

D1.7

Overview report of all annual meetings, General Assembly and Steering Committee meetings

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Deliverable abstract

The report contains an overview of all organised and held Annual Meetings, General Assembly and Steering Committee Meetings of the project. In addition, the meetings of the Board of European Environmental Research Infrastructures which is an advisory panel for ENVRI-FAIR are included.

Five ENVRI weeks were organized and held in February each project year. During the ENVRI weeks, meetings of the General Assembly and the Board of European Environmental Research Infrastructures took place. Meetings of the Steering Committee called the Executive Board were conducted at least quarterly, both face-to-face and as virtual meetings.

DELIVERY SLIP

	Name	Partner Organization	Date
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DELIVERY LOG

Issue	Date	Comment	Author
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DOCUMENT AMENDMENT PROCEDURE

Amendments, comments and suggestions should be sent to the Project Manager at manager@envri-fair.eu.

GLOSSARY

A relevant project glossary is included in Appendix A. The latest version of the master list of the glossary is available at <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3465753>.

PROJECT SUMMARY

ENVRI-FAIR is the connection of the ESFRI Cluster of Environmental Research Infrastructures (ENVRI) to the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). Participating research infrastructures (RI) of the environmental domain cover the subdomains Atmosphere, Marine, Solid Earth and Biodiversity / Ecosystems and thus the Earth system in its full complexity.

The overarching goal is that at the end of the proposed project, all participating RIs have built a set of FAIR data services which enhances the efficiency and productivity of researchers, supports innovation, enables data- and knowledge-based decisions, and connects the ENVRI Cluster to the EOSC.

This goal is reached by: (1) well defined community policies and standards on all steps of the data life cycle, aligned with the wider European policies, as well as with international developments; (2) each participating RI will have sustainable, transparent, and auditable data services, for each step of data life cycle, compliant to the FAIR principles. (3) the focus of the proposed work is put on the implementation of prototypes for testing pre-production services at each RI; the catalogue of prepared services is defined for each RI independently, depending on the maturity of the involved RIs; (4) the complete set of thematic data services and tools provided by the ENVRI cluster is exposed under the EOSC catalogue of services.

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D1.7 - Overview report of all annual meetings, General Assembly and Steering Committee meetings

1 Introduction

The overall governance structure and procedures on ENVRI-FAIR outlined in Figure 1 are based closely on the DESCA Horizon 2020 Model Consortium Agreement “Governance structure for Medium and Large Projects” outline (www.DESCA-2020.eu).

Figure 1: Overall management structure and procedures on ENVRI-FAIR

The ENVRI-FAIR consortium had two official bodies: the General Assembly (GA) and the Executive Board (EB). The GA is the decision-making body of the Consortium, where each beneficiary is responsible also for representing their linked third parties. GA is responsible for monitoring the project progress and use of resources as specified in the Consortium Agreement, approving, and removing consortium members and members of the Executive Board and approving amendments.

The Executive Board is the supervisory body for the execution of the project which shall report to and be accountable to the General Assembly.

The Board of European Environmental Research Infrastructures acts as advisory panel to ENVRI-FAIR. Note: In chapters 6 - General Assembly – and chapter 4 – Executive Board – links to documents in the internal Project Management System are given which are only available internally. For review purpose these can be provided on request.

2 ENVRI weeks - consortium meetings of ENVRI-FAIR

The consortium meetings of ENVRI-FAIR were called ENVRI weeks. They took place annually in the first week of February. The ENVRI weeks typically encompassed meetings of the General Assembly (GA), meetings of the Executive Board (EB) and meetings of the BEERi (see also corresponding chapters).

1. ENVRI-FAIR Kick-Off meeting, 14 – 16 January 2019, Prague, Czechia
2. ENVRI week 2020, 3 – 6 February 2020, Dresden, Germany
3. ENVRI week 2021, 1 – 5 February 2021, virtual meeting
4. ENVRI week 2022, 31 January – 4 February 2022, virtual meeting
5. ENVRI week 2023, 30 January – 3 February 2023, Leipzig, Germany

2.1 ENVRI week 2019

The ENVRI week 2019 was also the ENVRI-FAIR Kick-Off meeting. It took place 14 – 16 January 2019 in Prague, Czechia.

In the Kick-Off meeting the basic concepts of ENVRI-FAIR were introduced, including the Management Structure and Workflow, the project management system Redmine and all the work packages together with their tasks, deliverables, and milestones.

More information on the ENVRI-FAIR Kick-Off meeting can be found in deliverable [D1.1 - Organization of project Kick-off meeting, including a Steering Committee and a General Assembly meeting](#).

2.2 ENVRI week 2020

The ENVRI week 2020 took place 3 – 6 February 2020 in Dresden, Germany. In this meeting over 110 participants representing different Environmental Research Infrastructures, as well as attendees from external organisations and projects collaborating with our community attended more than 30 sessions.

The agenda of the ENVRI week 2020 can be found in Annex II – ENVRI week 2020 – Dresden, Germany.

2.3 ENVRI week 2021

Due to the COVID-19 pandemic the ENVRI week 2021 took place as virtual event 1 – 5 February 2021. In this meeting about 80 participants attended about 20 sessions which were organised mainly as plenary sessions. In these sessions for the different work packages the results, highlights and next steps were reported. In addition, the cross-domain Task Forces reported on the various challenges of their subjects, their achievements, and the collaboration/connection with other work packages.

The agenda of the ENVRI week 2021 can be found in Annex IV – ENVRI week 2021 – virtual meeting.

2.4 ENVRI week 2022

Due to the still ongoing COVID-19 pandemic the ENVRI week 2022 took also place as virtual event from 31 January to 4 February 2022. To shorten the time spent in online meetings in that year the workshops which usually took place during the ENVRI week were scheduled before or after the ENVRI week. In the ENVRI week 2022 about 80 participants attended in more than 15 sessions. A large part of the meeting was dedicated to the preparation of the project review where the results and achievements of ENVRI-FAIR were presented to the reviewers for the European Commission and the project officer from the Research Executive Agency (REA).

2.5 ENVRI week 2023

As the ENVRI-FAIR was extended by 6 months a fifth ENVRI week took place within the project. This meeting could again take place as a face-to-face meeting and was held in Leipzig, Germany. For the plenary sessions virtual attendance was also possible, but most participants were there in person and only a few attended virtually. About 80 participants attended about 20 sessions and workshops. This meeting was dedicated to discussing and planning the final steps of the work in ENVRI-FAIR. In addition, the subdomains presented their main achievements in FAIRness and their vision on further progressing it within the next five years.

3 General Assembly

In accordance with the Consortium Agreement (CA) the General Assembly met annually during the ENVRI weeks. These meetings were chaired by the project coordinator, Andreas Petzold.

1. 16 January 2019, Prague, Czech Republic
2. 5 February 2020, Dresden, Germany
3. 3 February 2021, virtual meeting
4. 1 February 2022, virtual meeting
5. 1 February 2023, Leipzig, Germany

3.1 1st GA meeting

The first meeting of the General Assembly took place on 16 January 2019 during the ENVRI week 2019, the Kick-Off meeting of ENVRI-FAIR, in Prague, Czech Republic. The agenda of this meeting is part of [D1.1 - Organization of project Kick-off meeting, including a Steering Committee and a General Assembly meeting](#). In this meeting the Terms of Reference (ToR) were agreed and the members of the Executive Board, the chairperson of the Executive Board and the co-coordinator of the project were appointed. In addition, the members of the Data Management Team were appointed, the financial aspects, including reporting periods, payments, eligibility of costs and reimbursement were explained. The requirements and contents for the continuous and periodic reporting were presented.

Meeting minutes

General Assembly opened 10:30; Slides are accessible [here](#)

1. Confirmation of Quorum
 - The quorum was reached with 29 out of 37 partners being represented.
2. Adoption of the Agenda for the meeting
 - The agenda was adopted by the present GA representatives.
3. Introducing the structure of General Assembly and its Terms of Reference
 - Proposal that virtual decisions will be taken as abstention if partner representatives do not respond within 21 days was accepted by GA.
 - Coordinator requested responsible nomination of partner representatives to ensure timely response to virtual decision requests.
 - The Terms of Reference were adopted with the modification mentioned above, otherwise as proposed by the coordinator.
4. Appointments of
 - Executive Board Members: Work package leaders were approved by GA.
 - Executive Board Chairperson: GA approved Executive Board Chair Person as elected in the upcoming Executive Board meeting.
 - Project Co-coordinator: GA approved Ari Asmi as project co-coordinator.
5. Conformation of the Data Management Team
 - The data management team is responsible for providing ENVRI-FAIR with Data Management Plans during the project period.
 - The management team consists of Co-coordinator (chair), MST representative (responsible of drafting the DMP text), and WP 5 and 7 leaders.
 - Co-coordinator: Ari Asmi
 - WP5 leader: Alex Vermeulen
 - WP7 leader: Zhiming Zhao
 - MST representative: to be nominated later
 - The GA approves the proposed membership of Data Management Team
6. Financial Administration and Reporting
 - Basic information on the financial administration will be available on Redmine.
 - Full details of reporting duties will be summarized on Redmine.
7. Communication Issues
 - Presentation by Magdalena Brus is available [here](#).
8. Amendments

Presentation on requirements of Amendments is available [here](#).

9. Meeting schedule

- Proposal for one annual meeting to be organized in (mid) May during the annual meeting was approved by GA.
- Detailed time schedule will be prepared by the Executive Board.

10. Any other business

- No other business raised by GA representatives.

3.2 2nd GA meeting

The second GA meeting took place during the ENVRI week 2020 in Dresden, Germany on 5 February 2020.

Meeting minutes

1. Opening of the meeting

Andreas Petzold welcomed the participants.

2. Adoption of the agenda for the meeting

The Members of the General Assembly have received the agenda in time as stated in the Consortium agreement. No additional topics were added to agenda item 12 (AOB).

The agenda was adopted (none of the participant representatives voted against, no abstentions).

The quorum (n=25) was reached, as 29 of 37 participants were represented (see list of participant representatives).

3. Progress report by the project administration

- Report by Andreas Petzold on:
 - Deliverables
 - Milestones
 - Project representation at EU and international level
 - Reflection on Project Status
- 3 deliverables are pending, 3 deliverables are postponed (the EC project officer has approved/ is informed about the postponing).
- Key deliverables:
 - D2.1 Dissemination strategy for ENVRI-FAIR project
 - FAIRness assessments and implementations plan by the subdomains
 - D5.1 Requirement analysis, technology review and gap analysis of environmental RIs
- Most milestones which were due in 2019 are reached, 5 milestones are postponed, one is pending.
- Reflection on project status:
 - The project progressed well during the first year. Gaps were identified and we know how to proceed.
 - Subdomain progress:
 - Discussions within the subdomains are leading to a common understanding.
 - Implementation plans are prepared, with great help of horizontal WP5 and WP7 (special thanks to Alex and Zhiming).
 - Very fruitful FAIRness review workshop took place in Lund in October and impressive FAIRNESS assessment (D5.1) will be finished by the end of February 2020.
 - So far work has taken place mainly within the subdomains. We now need to promote cross-subdomain collaboration.

Andreas highlighted that immediate response by WPs is highly appreciated, as delayed responses slow down the project progress.

Sylvie Pouliquen commented that in the next ENVRI week we need to discuss cross-subdomain topics apart from the task force work (i.e., on a strategy level instead of exclusively on a technical level).

4. Appointment of new EB members (Nicola Fiore and Jacco Konijn in WP6, Anca Hienola in WP3)

Nicola Fiore and Jacco Konijn were appointed unanimously as new Executive Board Members (replacing Alberto Basset (LifeWatch ERIC) as co-leads of WP6)

Anca Hienola was appointed unanimously as new Executive Board Member (co-leading WP3).

5. Appointment of EB chair for the project year 2020 (proposed: Cathrine Lund Myhre)

Cathrine Lund Myhre was appointed unanimously as Executive Board Chair for the project year 2020.

6. First Periodic Report (procedure, timeline)

Daniela Franz (ENVRI-FAIR Project manager) introduced the planned procedure and timeline for the first periodic report.

Helen Graves commented that the proposed timeline is not realistic, as the reporting falls into the holiday season.

Ari Asmi suggested to have the technical reports for each WP prepared by end of June 2020.

Andreas Petzold added that Redmine is mandatory for the reporting process, in order to allow the project management to track the progress.

It was agreed that the first drafts of the technical reports for each WP have to be ready by the end of June 2020. Some of the deliverables and milestones are due at the same time. Their outcomes can be included in the reports during the review of the reports.

7. Remarks from the financial administration

Daniela Franz reported on remarks from the financial administration and highlighted that the financial administration will need one contact person for the financial reporting.

Andreas Petzold requested that each participant checks that the contact person for financial issues is stated in the EU Portal.

Andreas Petzold commented that the WPs will be contacted in case of any deviations in the use of resources.

8. Mid-term review (announcement and preparation)

Daniela Franz reported about the planning of the mid-term review.

It was questioned by the audience what key deliverables and key WP leads mean. Daniela said it was not specified by the EC project officer. Andreas Petzold commented that all WPs have to be represented by at least one lead or co-lead. The key deliverables have to be identified during the EB strategy meeting, for which the representation of all WPs is requested.

9. Communications

Magdalena Brus presented the results of the Mentimeter survey conducted during the Communications session on Monday.

Jacco Konijn asked to let him know about any events/ side meetings at conferences etc. planned.

It was discussed if a training on how to tweet should be offered for RI managers/ directors.

Jacco Konijn announced the participation at the RDA Conference in Melbourne in March and asked who will attend the event (Helen Graves, Anca Hienola). Helen asked to send her an email in case more people are attending.

Andreas Petzold commented that the participation in conferences etc. will be collected in Redmine.

Magdalena asked the audience to read the Newsletters to check for updates on templates etc.

10. Status of Amendment I/ announcement of Amendment II

Daniela Franz reported on the status of Amendment I, which was approved by the GA. Currently, pending documents are collected, the submission of the amendment is planned for next week.

Helen Graves withdrew the need for an UKRI/ CEH related case for a second amendment.

Daniela highlighted that any need for a second amendment needs to be announced until end of February 2020, in order to finish the amendment before the end of the first reporting period).

11. Upcoming meetings

Andreas Petzold announced upcoming internal and external meetings.

The event planned in Brussels by WP3 for national and international Stakeholders is missing.

Helen Glaves asked about the expectations towards the WP leads to attend the EB Strategy meeting, as there are overlapping events. Andreas commented that this will be discussed in the EB meeting in the afternoon.

12. AOB

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3.3 3rd GA meeting

The third GA meeting was held on 3 February 2021 like the ENVRI week 2021 as a virtual meeting.

Meeting minutes

1. Opening of the meeting

Andreas Petzold welcomed the participants.

2. Adoption of the agenda for the meeting and minutes of the last meeting

The agenda was adopted, and the meeting minutes of the last meeting accepted.

The quorum (minimum number of represented partners =25) was reached, as 33 of 39 participants were represented (see list of participant representatives).

3. Status of the project

Andreas Petzold reported on

- a. Deliverables
- b. Milestones
- c. Project meetings
- d. Project representation at EU and international level
- e. Reflection on Project Status

1. 2 deliverables are pending, 2 deliverables are postponed (the EC project officer has approved/ is informed about the postponing).
2. Most milestones which were due in 2020 are reached, 2 milestones are postponed.
3. Reflection on project status:

The project progressed well during the second year in spite of the COVID-19 pandemic.

4. Proposal of new EB members (proposed: Angeliki Adamaki and Claudio Dema for WP5, Ulpu Leijala for WP3)

Angeliki Adamaki and Claudio Dema were appointed unanimously as new Executive Board Members (co-leads for WP5)

Ulpu Leijala was appointed unanimously as new Executive Board Member (co-leading WP3).

5. Proposal of EB chair for the project year 2021 (proposed: Helen Glaves)

Helen Glaves was appointed as Executive Board Chair for the project year 2021 with one abstention and no vote against.

6. ENVRI Communications

Magdalena Brus had already presented the report on the ENVRI communications in a previous ENVRI week session. In this GA meeting she asked for feedback on the communication activities, results of the online survey are given [here](#).

7. Overview on the financial status

Katrin Seemeyer gave an overview on the financial status (see [file](#)). After the first reporting period on average 18% of the planned costs were spent which would be less than what could be sent (37,5 %)

8. Second Periodic Report

Katrin Seemeyer introduced the planned procedure and timeline for the second periodic report. As some deadlines are in holiday seasons it was suggested to adapt the timeline accordingly.

9. Midterm review (timeline and preparation)

Katrin Seemeyer reported on the planning of the midterm review. As the EC suggested to postpone the midterm review to M38 (Feb 2022) this would rather be a project review. By then the administrative tasks will be delegated to the REA. But their views on timeline and requirements are still unclear. But preparation will start about 6 months before the review.

10. Status of Amendment III

The third amendment to the grant agreement was accepted by the General Assembly (23 voted yes, no veto). In addition, beneficiaries can adapt due dates of milestones and deliverables, if it is already foreseeable that they will be delayed. As a lot of travel cost could not be used due to the COVID-19 measures it would also be possible to shift travel cost to personnel costs. For these two items no amendment is necessary, but it would look better to the REA.

If any partner would like to adapt the numbers, please contact Katrin Seemeyer (k.seemeyer@fz-juelich.de).

11. AOB

Andreas Petzold asked if the partners are satisfied with the work of the management team. It was commented that the project partners are fully satisfied with the work of the management team.

3.4 4th GA meeting

Due to the ongoing pandemic situation the fourth GA meeting at the ENVRI week 2022 was also held as a virtual meeting.

Meeting minutes

1. Opening of the meeting

Andreas Petzold welcomed the participants.

2. Adoption of the agenda for the meeting and minutes of the last meeting

The agenda was adopted, and the meeting minutes of the last meeting accepted.

The quorum (minimum number or represented partners =25) was reached, as 33 of 39 participants were represented (see list of participant representatives).

3. Status of the project

Andreas Petzold and Katrin Seemeyer reported on

- f. Key achievements ([file](#), slide 4-5)
- g. Important dates ([file](#), slide 6)
- h. Open tasks ([file](#), slide 7)
- i. Overview and reporting ([file](#), slide 8-9)
- j. Deliverables ([file](#), slide 10-11)
- k. Milestones ([file](#), slide 12-13)

- l. Amendments ([file](#), slide 14)
- m. Project meetings and Project representation at EU and international level ([file](#), slide 15)
- n. Reflection on Project Status

4. Proposal of new co-coordinator (proposed: Anca Hienola)

As Ari Asmi left the University of Helsinki for his new position as Director of RDA Europe he stepped down as the co-coordinator of ENVRI-FAIR.

Anca Hienola was appointed unanimously as new co-coordinator of ENVRI-FAIR.

5. Proposal of EB chair for the project year 2022 (proposed: Alberto Basset)

Alberto Basset was appointed as Executive Board Chair for the project year 2022 with one abstention and no vote against.

6. Proposal of new EB members (proposed: Peter Thijsse for WP7, Katri Ahlgren for WP2)

Peter Thijsse was appointed unanimously as new Executive Board Members (co-lead for WP7).

Katri Ahlgren was appointed unanimously as new Executive Board Members (interim lead for WP2)

7. ENVRI Communications

As Magdalena Brus left ENVRI-FAIR for her new position as communications lead at the EGI, Katri Ahlgren and Karlina Ozolina took over her tasks ad interim until a new person for this position is found. Katri presented some basic information about herself and Karlina and the work for communication planned ([file](#), slide 20).

Afterwards it was discussed whether ENVRI-FAIR should have a physical booth at the EGU. The meeting in Vienna, Austria this year will be hybride meeting. The booth should be used to promote the ENVRI-Hub. In addition, many people from ENVRI-FAIR will be there a physical booth will be very useful.

8. Overview on the financial status

Katrin Seemeyer gave an overview on the financial status ([file](#), slide 21).

9. AOB

Andreas Petzold asked if the partners are satisfied with the work of the management team. It was commented that the project partners are fully satisfied with the work of the management team.

3.5 5th GA meeting

The fifth and last GA meeting could again be held as a face-to-face meeting during the ENVRI week 2023. There was also the option to participate remotely.

Meeting minutes

1. Opening of the meeting, quorum

Andreas Petzold welcomed the participants. The quorum (minimum number or represented partners =26) was reached, as 28 of 39 participants were represented (see list of participant representatives).

2. Adoption of the agenda for the meeting and minutes of the last meeting

The agenda was adopted, and the meeting minutes of the last meeting accepted.

3. Appointment of a chair for the Executive Board in 2023

Anca Hienola was elected as the chair for the Executive Board in 2023. She accepted the election.

4. Status of the project

Andreas Petzold and Katrin Seemeyer reported on

- o. Summary of important accomplishments ([file](#), slide 5-7)
- p. Open tasks ([file](#), slide 8)
- q. Overview and reporting ([file](#), slide 9-10)
- r. Important dates ([file](#), slide 11)
- s. Deliverables Q1 2023 ([file](#), slide 12)
- t. Milestones ([file](#), slide 13)
- u. Amendments ([file](#), slide 14)
- v. Project meetings and Project representation at EU and international level ([file](#), slide 15)

5. ENVRI Communications

Katri presented an overview on the communication activities in 2022 and the results of the survey done on Monday in the communications session on the communications activities in ENVRI-FAIR (file, slide 16-31).

6. Sustainability of products beyond ENVRI-FAIR

Andreas presented the activities for the sustainability of the products of ENVRI-FAIR beyond the project ([file](#), slide 32-37).

7. AOB

none

4 Executive Board (Steering Committee)

The Steering Committee or ENVRI-FAIR was the Executive Board (EB) consisting of all work package (WP) leads and co-leads as their deputies. In accordance with the Consortium Agreement EB meetings took place quarterly and since 2020 more often. In the first meeting each year the EB elected a new chair from another subdomain. In 2019 the chair was Juan José Dañobeitia (marine subdomain), in 2020 Cathrine Lund Myhre (atmospheric subdomain), in 2021 Helen Glaves (solid earth subdomain) and in 2022 Alberto Basset (biodiversity and ecosystem subdomain), in the 2023, the last half year of ENVRI-FAIR, the co-coordinator of ENVRI-FAIR – Anca Hienola - was also the chair of the Executive Board.

1. 1st EB meeting, 16 January 2019, Prague, Czech Republic at the Kick-Off Meeting
2. 2nd EB meeting, 22 August 2019 (replaced by EB report)
3. 3rd EB meeting, 1 October 2019, Amsterdam, NL
4. 4th EB meeting, 3 December 2019, virtual
5. 5th EB meeting, 5 February 2020, Dresden, DE
6. EB Strategy meeting, 7 April 2020, virtual
7. 6th EB meeting, 25 August 2020, virtual
8. 7th EB meeting, 20 October 2020, virtual
9. 8th EB meeting, 8 January 2021, virtual
10. 9th EB meeting, 3 February 2021, virtual
11. 10th EB meeting, 30 March 2021, virtual
12. 11th EB meeting, 25 May 2021, virtual
13. 12th EB meeting, 27 July 2021, virtual
14. 13th EB meeting, 28 September 2021, virtual
15. 14th EB meeting, 30 November 2021, virtual
16. 15th EB meeting, 25 January 2022, virtual
17. 16th EB meeting, 2 February 2022, virtual at the ENVRI week 2022
18. 17th EB meeting, 29 March 2022, virtual
19. 18th EB meeting, 31 May 2022, virtual
20. 19th EB meeting, 27 July 2022, virtual
21. 20th EB meeting, 27 September 2022, virtual
22. 21st EB meeting, 29 November 2022, virtual
23. 22nd EB meeting, 31 January 2023, Leipzig, DE at the ENVRI week 2023
24. 23rd EB meeting, 28 March 2023, virtual
25. 24th EB meeting, 31 May 2023, virtual

4.1 1st EB meeting

The first Executive Board meeting took place during the ENVRI week 2019, the Kick-Off meeting of ENVRI-FAIR, in Prague, Czech Republic.

Meeting minutes

1. Approval of Agenda
 - The proposed agenda was approved after adding of the topic “ENVRI-FAIR @ESFRI-EOSC Liaison Workshop, London” to Any Other Business”.
2. Election of a Chairperson
 - A procedure was proposed to elect the EB chairs Domain wise like in ENVRIplus, starting with Marine, then Solid Earth, Ecosystems, and Atmosphere.
 - The Marine domain suggests Juan José Dañobeitia as first chair person.
 - EB elects Juan José Dañobeitia by unanimous vote; he accepted the election.
3. Discussion of the draft ToR
 - A clarification was requested that each WP has one vote in the EB, independent for the numbers of representatives present.
 - A clarification was requested that all additions to the distributed Agenda which are submitted after 21 day will be put in the AOB.
 - ToR are accepted by EB
4. Meeting schedule (4 times per year)
 - The EB agreed to two virtual and two face-to-face meetings per year with the meeting prior to the GA being face-to-face.
 - Amsterdam meeting facilities at the airport are a good location; facilities are closed for 6 Month, so alternatives are needed for that period; schedule and location need to be approved by EB on a case by case basis until the facilities are available again.
 - Technical equipment and virtual platform will be organized by the Project Management Team.
 - The final ENVRIplus week will be taken as an opportunity for ad-hoc meeting even if there is not much to discuss at that time.
 - Dissemination Event in Brussels in June is confirmed for next EB meeting.
5. Review of the Kick-Off Meeting and decision on potential actions if required
6. Responsibility in Project Monitoring
 - Monitoring the implementation process is WP 5 responsibility
 - Executive summary provided to the EB every 6 Month
 - Determining responsibility for definition of cross domain services
 - Coordination requests coordinated process to make sure to having an aligned development across domains.
 - WP 5 / WP7 representatives indicate that need for cross domain services has to be a bottom up approach.
 - Coordination notes that a scientifically interesting story is needed in addition to a technically driven one.
 - WP3/4 proposes scouting this process and starting consultation with Copernicus for user needs.
 - WP8-11 may discuss internally and come up with some ideas to EB002E
7. Representation of the project on the EU and international levels
 - Proposal from Project Coordination:
 1. ESFRI - > Coordinator
 2. EOSC (related technical)-> DMT members (WP 5/7)
 3. FAIR policies related projects -> WP4
 4. Organizational client (Copernicus) -> WP3

5. Sub-domains and RI are in charge as well
Proposal is accepted by EB.

8. Coordination team proposed to coordinate presentations and collect given presentations:

- Key messages presentation and overview presentations will be provided by WP2
- Every presentation given about ENVRI Fair has to be stored centrally by WP2 to keep track/record on what is shown.
- Calendar of presentation :-> post an “issue” in WP2 Redmine subproject such that WP2 can keep track on the presentations.
- All EB Members should provide information to which international meeting they will contribute (linked to ENVRI-FAIR issues).

Proposal is accepted by EB

9. Next meeting

- Next meeting is fixed back-to-back to the ENVRIplus Dissemination Event in June
- September slot to be defined for Virtual Meeting
- 3 December 2019 set for face-to-face meeting
- 3 -7 February 2020 for ENVRI-FAIR Week

10. Any other business

- Information and is provided to the EB members about the ESFRI RIs and EOSC Workshop in London on 30 January 2019.
- Information is available at <https://www.esfri.eu/esfri-events/esfri-ris-eosc-liaison-workshop>.
- Presentations are available at <https://www.esfri.eu/esfri-events/esfri-ris-eosc-liaison-workshop?qt-event=5#qt-even>

4.2 2nd EB meeting, 22 August 2019 (replaced by EB report)

Project Status Report to the Executive Board

This status report of the Project Management Team replaces the 2nd Meeting of the EB, which was scheduled back-to-back to the ENVRIplus Dissemination Event in June; see the minutes of the first EB meeting in the Appendix 1.

The report reviews the status of the project after six months duration of ENVRI-FAIR.

1. Project Management Team

On 1 June 2019 Daniela Franz, formerly working at the ICOS ERIC Head Office started her duties as ENVRI-FAIR project manager at Forschungszentrum Juelich GmbH (FZJ). Daniela knows the members of the ENVRI cluster from her work on the ENVRIplus Landscape Analysis (ENVRIplus D17.6 - Landscape analysis) and is thus very well prepared for this challenging task.

On 1 July 2019, Ines Thelen completed the project management team by assisting Daniela in the day to day business and helping with communication tasks.

Both new members of the Project Management Team are warmly welcome!

Now the Project Management Team is complete and we want to introduce the members:

Project Coordinator Andreas Petzold ✉ a.petzold@fz-juelich.de

Project Co-Coordinator Ari Asmi ✉ ari.asmi@helsinki.fi

Project Manager Daniela Franz ✉ d.franz@fz-juelich.de; manager@envri-fair.eu

<i>Administrative Support</i>	Ines Thelen	✉ i.thelen@fz-juelich.de
<i>Project Administration</i>	Petra Insberg	✉ p.insberg@fz-juelich.de
<i>Financial Administration</i>	Claudia de Laat	✉ c.de.laat@fz-juelich.de
<i>Data Manager (Redmine)</i>	Ulrich Bundke	✉ u.bundke@fz-juelich.de

Communication Lines

- All communication to the project management team should be directed to both the coordinator and manager. They will then forward your request to the responsible team members.
- Be aware that all ENVRI-FAIR related communication to the European Commission has to go through the Project Coordination.
- Communication for project reporting will go through the Project Administration.
- Communication for financial reporting will go through the Financial Administration.
- Requests for Redmine related issues should be sent directly to the Data Manager.

2. Project Communication Tools

a. Redmine

ENVRI-FAIR uses the open-source Redmine environment for storage of project-related contact information of participants and project-related documents, for handling the communication between participants, for coordinating workflows in work packages and for the project management. The system is a password-protected and secured system for project data storage. The access is controlled, and can be specified for specific times. The system is hosted at Forschungszentrum Juelich GmbH. The Data Protection Officer of FZJ included ENVRI-FAIR Redmine into the FZJ Data Protection directory of procedures.

The project communication platform has been established and currently, the ENVRI-FAIR user group has 150 members. [ENVRI-FAIR D1.2 Project Internal Communication Tool](#) contains the details about the tool and its structure.

Relevant links to Redmine

- General system description <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Redmine>
- Detailed features <https://www.redmine.org/projects/redmine/wiki/Features>
- ENVRI-FAIR tool <https://iagos-comm.iek.fz-juelich.de/projects/envri-fair>

For access to Redmine and questions, please contact the Data Manager Ulrich Bundke ✉ u.bundke@fz-juelich.de.

b. Website

Today, the website is still in its preliminary version accessible at <http://envri.eu/envri-fair/>. The domain name envri-fair.eu and related domains are secured for later use.

It is agreed with WP2, that the main website will be kept under the ENVRI community at envri.eu and the ongoing and finished projects ENVRI-FAIR and ENVRIplus will be integrated. This concept keeps the branding and highlights ENVRI-FAIR as the current main activity of the ENVRI community.

c. Templates for reports and presentations

Templates for

- ENVRI-FAIR presentations, and
- Meeting agendas and minutes

are accessible at

https://iagos-comm.iek.fz-juelich.de/projects/general-documents/dmsf?folder_id=227.

When you prepare reports or presentations, please check this folder for the latest version.

d. Overview presentations

We provide two versions of overview presentations:

- Short version (11 slides)
- Extended version (20 slides)

The current versions of both overview presentations are accessible at

https://iagos-comm.iek.fz-juelich.de/projects/general-documents/dmsf?folder_id=216.

Whenever you want to use an overview presentation, please check this folder for the latest version. We will update the presentations continuously.

3. Meetings

a. Common event and meeting calendar

In ENVRI-FAIR many meetings are held virtually. Our personal calendars and carbon footprints are thankful. In order to not lose track of the meeting schedules and the activities in the project, the WP (co)leads are kindly asked to provide information on the existence of regular and irregular meetings within and across WPs. Furthermore, we kindly ask the WP (co)leads to share information on upcoming events such as conferences, workshops and submission deadlines. This information is, in particular, important for an optimal coordination of outreach activities and the upcoming reporting to the European Commission.

We have set up a dedicated subproject within Redmine, which includes information on

- meetings (issue tracker "Meeting"),
- conferences and workshops (issue tracker "Feature"), and
- deadlines for abstract and proposal submissions (issue tracker "Scheduled Task").

Please have a look at the calendar and Gantt features to get informed. You can filter the issues according to the tracker mentioned above.

The project manager will enter the meetings and events into the calendar. Please provide information about past and upcoming events and meetings, including

- a list of persons who are attending the meeting or event,
- a link to the conference / workshop / deadline announcement, and
- a link to or file containing the respective abstract etc.

b. Regular meetings across WPs

Information exchange across the different WPs is crucial for the success of the project. The following regular virtual meetings are already set up:

- Monthly meeting of WPs 5-7
- Monthly meetings of WPs 5-11
- Monthly meetings of WPs 1-4 (co) leads (leads of WPs 5 and 7 are invited to join)

The specific dates will be added soon to the common meeting calendar.

c. Meeting scheduler

Deutsches Forschungsnetz (DFN) offers a freely accessible platform to coordinate possible meetings with a poll. The tool is accessible here: <https://terminplaner4.dfn.de/>.

The tool is self-explanatory and offers the possibility to write comments, which is helpful for the participants to mention overlaps with other meetings etc.

Once you have confirmed the creation of your poll, you will receive two emails: one containing the link of your poll for sending to the participants, the other containing the link to the poll administration page.

d. Virtual meeting rooms

DFN also offers a platform to create virtual meeting rooms (similar to WebEx, Skype etc.) to all institutes participating in DFN such as FZJ. We created a separate meeting room for each single WP, which can be used for meetings across WPs or with external participants. The meeting rooms can be used multiple times. It is not possible to have two meetings at the same time in the same meeting room.

More information is available in Redmine, including the guest PINs for using the rooms:
<https://iagos-comm.iek.fz-juelich.de/projects/contact-information/wiki>.

The PINs for the meeting organisers (hosts) will be provided separately to the WP (co)leads via email.

e. Meeting minutes

The project office kindly asks the organisers of virtual or F2F meetings to take notes during the meeting or to delegate this task to another participant, and to share the minutes in Redmine, preferably in the DMSF of the respective WP. The minutes should include a list of the main discussion points and conclusions/ decisions as well as action points and will help everybody to keep track on the activities in the project.

A respective template as well as a template to create meeting agendas can be found here:
https://iagos-comm.iek.fz-juelich.de/projects/general-documents/dmsf?folder_id=227.

4. Report on Communications Actions

The project office kindly asks all project partners to prepare short reports for communications actions with regard to ENVRI-FAIR (e.g., conference participation, conference paper, poster, social media, presentation, articles published in the popular press). Reporting is part of the dissemination strategy by WP2 <https://iagos-comm.iek.fz-juelich.de/dmsf/files/3646/view> and needs to be collected anyway for each reporting period.

A preliminary template for the reports can be found in Redmine:
https://iagos-comm.iek.fz-juelich.de/projects/task-2-1-development-and-implementation-of-the-envri-fair-communication-strategy/dmsf?folder_id=286.

Please store the reports for now in this folder. An online form will replace the template soon.

5. Amendment Opened

An amendment procedure has been opened. It will cover the following actions:

1. Adding Participant 17 (UKRI) to WP2 and 11
2. Adding Participant 27 (UvA) to WP6
3. Adding linked third parties to participant 10 (EMSO ERIC) for activities in WP3, 4, 9 and 10
4. Adding a linked third party to participant 10 (EMSO ERIC) for activities in WP10 (needs to be confirmed by participant)
5. Adding linked third parties to participant 11 (LifeWatch ERIC) for activities in WP11
6. Adding a linked third party to participant 23 (USTIR) for activities in WP11

There have been requests for several small modifications and budget shifts between partners, but without affecting the work programme. These budget shifts will be included in the Amendment to the GA and the required modification of the Description of Action.

Concerned participants have been contacted by the project management, which is currently preparing the documents for the amendment. We are working towards presenting the Amendment at the next EB meeting.

6. EB Meetings

Status of scheduled EB meetings:

- 2nd EB meeting: Originally planned back-to-back to the ENVRIplus Dissemination Event in June, is replaced by this report.
- 3rd EB meeting: scheduled as F2F meeting on 1 October 2019 in Amsterdam Schiphol; further information will be shared soon.
- 4th EB meeting: during the first EB meeting, 3 December 2019 was set for face-to-face meeting; we suggest organising a virtual meeting.

- ENVRI-FAIR week 2020: scheduled for 3 -7 February 2020; currently potential venues are investigated. ENVRI-FAIR weeks are likewise scheduled for the first full week in February in 2021 and 2022.

7. Deliverables and Milestones

According to the definitions provided by the EC in the proposal templates:

Deliverable means a distinct output of the project, meaningful in terms of the project's overall objectives and constituted by a report, a document, a technical diagram, a software etc.

Milestone means control points in the project that help to chart progress. Milestones may correspond to the completion of a key deliverable, allowing the next phase of the work to begin. They may also be needed at intermediary points so that, if problems have arisen, corrective measures can be taken. A milestone may be a critical decision point in the project where, for example, the consortium must decide which of several technologies to adopt for further development. Reaching a milestone is documented by a short internal report and a brief statement which is added to the project continuous reporting; see Table 2 for examples.

Upload your deliverable or milestone report to
<https://iagos-comm.iek.fz-juelich.de/projects/reporting/dmsf>.

using the templates accessible at
https://iagos-comm.iek.fz-juelich.de/projects/general-documents/dmsf?folder_id=227.

The project reporting is mostly on time with only two deliverables being slightly delayed. At the end of Month 6, 11 Milestones had been due which were all met. All subdomain work packages have conducted their subdomain FAIRness analyses and drafted preliminary implementation plans. Work packages 5 und 7, which coordinate the implementation work, have organised subdomain workshops for drafting the next steps towards detailed implementation plans. Work packages 5 and 7 have set up regular telephone calls with the subdomain work packages 8 to 11 to monitor and guide the implementation work in the subdomains. Table 1 and Table 2 contain the current status of Deliverables and Milestones, respectively.

The Deliverables and Milestone reports can be found in the following Redmine folder:
<https://iagos-comm.iek.fz-juelich.de/projects/reporting/dmsf>.

Table 1 List of submitted and upcoming Deliverables

WP	Deliverable	Title	Lead	Type	Due Date	Submission
WP1	D1.1	Organization of project Kick-off meeting	FZJ	Public	31 Mar 2019	25 Mar 2019
WP4	D4.1	Organisation of the Policy Working Group	UKRI	Public	31 Mar 2019	01 Apr 2019
WP12	D12.1	Protection of personal data	FZJ	Confidential	31 Mar 2019	29 Mar 2019
WP2	D2.1	Dissemination strategy	ICOS ERIC	Public	30. Apr 2019	02. Jul 2019
WP1	D1.2	Project internal communication	FZJ	Public	30. Jun 2019	28. Jun 2019
WP1	D1.3	Initial Data Management Plan	FZJ	Public	30. Jun 2019	29. Jun 2019
WP9	D9.1	Marine subdomain FAIRness roadmap	MARIS	Public	30. Jun 2019	Pending
WP6	D6.1	Inventory & gap analysis of FAIR training materials	ULUND	Public	31. Aug 2019	On time
WP8	D8.1	Atmospheric subdomain FAIRness assessment	UVSQ	Public	30. Sep 2019	On time
WP9	D9.2	Marine subdomain implementation plan	MARIS	Public	30. Sep 2019	On time

WP	Deliverable	Title	Lead	Type	Due Date	Submission
WP9	D9.6	Marine subdomain EOVS product specification	MARIS	Public	30. Sep 2019	On time

Table 2 List of reached and upcoming Milestones

MS	Title	Lead	Due Date	Reached	Comment
36	Kick-off workshop for Atmospheric RI technological implementation plan	NILU	31 Jan 2019	31 Jan 2019	The Kick-Off Workshop for Atmospheric RI technological implementation plan was held during the project Kick-Off meeting on 15 January 2019. Meeting minutes are archived for ENVRI-FAIR internal use.
1	ENVRI-FAIR website launched and first set of communications materials available	ICOS ERIC	31 Mar 2019	31 Mar 2019	The website is launched as sub-page to the ENVRI community page. Moving the ENVRI-FAIR and ENVRI community sites jointly to a new provider is in preparation.
5	Re-nomination of BEERI members and first BEERi meeting held during the ENVRI-FAIR Bi-annual meeting of BEERI	FMI	30 Jun 2019	26 Jun 2019	The first BEERi meeting during the ENVRI-FAIR project was held on 16-17 January 2019 in Prague, Czech Republic, directly after the ENVRI-FAIR kick-off meeting. This BEERi meeting included an agenda point on ENVRI-FAIR, where ENVRI-FAIR project kick-off outcomes, planned activities, and BEERi's connection to the project through the WP3 activities were discussed. BEERi memberships continued as they were in ENVRIplus.
21	Gap analysis, based on the inventory of existing training materials and a survey of target groups' needs, completed	ULUND	30 Jun 2019	28 Jun 2019	The gap analysis is based on two main sources of information: 1) the responses to a WP6-administered questionnaire on the needs and requirements of partner RIs with respect to training on general FAIR-related topics and more specific aspects of research data management (RDM), and 2) a web search for already existing teaching materials and courses related to the same topics. Trends are distinguished in the survey responses and the training resource inventory indicates that there are many openly accessible materials on general FAIR-related topics, but far less on more and specific topics.
28	The ENVRI-FAIR Knowledge Base web	UvA	30 Jun 2019	29 Jun 2019	The knowledge base is online accessible in a preliminary version at: kb.oil-e.net (a proper domain name will be implemented soon). In this version, there is initial content from ENVRIplus, and links to, e.g., the service portfolio. A dedicated working group works continuously on the development of the knowledge base.
29	Plan agreed for the co-development and technical workshops	UvA	30 Jun 2019	29 Jun 2019	During the technical implementation workshops of the individual subdomains (WP8, 9, 10 and 11), where also WP5 and WP7 participated, the co-development

MS	Title	Lead	Due Date	Reached	Comment
					and technical workshops were planned.
30	Kick off for case collection and test plan	MARIS	30 Jun 2019	29 Jun 2019	During the technical implementation workshops of the individual subdomains (WP8, 9, 10 and 11), where also WP5 and WP7 participated, the procedure to collect use cases was agreed. In addition, MARIS has started to work on the case of collection workflows.
34	Existing policies and licenses in use in the Atmospheric subdomain	UVSQ	30 Jun 2019	28 Jun 2019	Reference material for both data licence and data policy used by the 5 Atmosphere RIs ACTRIS, EISCAT, IAGOS, ICOS-Atm, SIOS was collected and is made accessible to the Atmospheric Subdomain in WP8.
35	Implementation plan defining the starting point – initial version	NILU	30 Jun 2019	28 Jun 2019	The implementation plan defining the starting point was developed during the first progress workshop in Amsterdam, 11th-12th June 2019; see MS 37 for details.
37	First progress workshop for Atmospheric RI technological implementation plan	NILU	30 Jun 2019	28 Jun 2019	The first progress workshop took place from 11th to 12th June 2019 in Amsterdam with 19 participants. The FAIRness assessment of the involved RIs was discussed and the starting point for the implementation plan defined. The meeting minutes and presentations are archived for ENVRI-FAIR internal use.
52	Criteria for FAIRness gap analysis of Marine subdomain agreed	MARIS	30 Jun 2019	29 Jun 2019	A two-step FAIRness survey has been conducted with all five marine RIs. First responses were reviewed during the technical implementation workshop of the marine subdomain in Amsterdam in May 2019, which yield a better understanding of several questions from the survey with support of the Dutch GO-FAIR office. Subsequently, all marine RIs reviewed and amended their original survey reports, which should include direct answers concerning the current situation and extra information about ideas, existing plans or implementation steps they have for improving FAIRness to correct current weaknesses and add more strengths. The analysis of the FAIRness strengths and weaknesses of each RI was conducted with the help of the YAML tool methodology. Solutions to address weaknesses proposed by the RIs will be evaluated, which will challenge the RIs to provide more structured plans for improving the FAIRness of their RIs, leading to the FAIRness Roadmap.
65	Criteria for FAIRness gap analysis of Solid Earth subdomain agreed	INGV	30 Jun 2019	26 Jun 2019	An assessment of the FAIRness of the RIs has been conducted through a questionnaire. All responses to the questionnaire have been human-interpreted to schematize and

MS	Title	Lead	Due Date	Reached	Comment
					harmonize the common ones, which permits the usage of questionnaires as a benchmark for performing a semi-automated evaluation, thus providing measurable criteria for gap analysis. In addition, a virtual meeting was conducted to involve the community and increase their awareness around the long walk to the FAIRification process.
93	Criteria for FAIRness gap analysis of Biodiversity and Ecosystem subdomain agreed	LifeWatch ERIC	30 Jun 2019	29 Jun 2019	During a meeting in Lecce (Italy) on June 27th-28th, where also WP5-7 participated, a first review of the current situation in terms of FAIRness for the different RIs was conducted. The approach for a more detailed and specific analysis and its main aspects were defined. The analysis will be used to plan the actions in Task 11.3.

4.3 3rd EB meeting, 1 October 2019, Amsterdam, NL

Meeting minutes

1. Approval of agenda/ Proposal for the acceptance of new WP6 co-leads for the EB (subject to final approval by the next GA)
 - The agenda was approved by the EB, one topic was added by the Project Office to Topic 10 (AOB): Request for the approval to publish Annex I of the Grant Agreement (non-confidential contents).
 - The proposal for two new WP6 co-leads (Jacco Konijn and Nicola Fiore) for the EB was accepted without any objection.
2. Update by the Project Office
 - **EB report (Andreas, Daniela):**
 - Major parts of the EB report were feeding into the first internal newsletter (WP2)
 - EB members are asked to check for the latest version in Redmine whenever using one of the templates or overview presentations (<https://iagos-comm.iek.fz-juelich.de/projects/general-documents/dmsf>).
 - EB members are asked to provide reports on communications actions, i.e. travel reports for past and future events (template available and reports stored here: https://iagos-comm.iek.fz-juelich.de/projects/task-2-1-development-and-implementation-of-the-envri-fair-communication-strategy/dmsf?folder_id=286; template will soon be available as online form on the webpage; report are important for project reporting and WP2)
 - Ari and Andreas will provide examples for their past travels
 - EB members are asked to share any information of past and upcoming ENVRI-FAIR relevant meetings, events and deadlines with Daniela, who will enter the events into the Redmine calendar
 - Important are information on who is going to the event and a link to the respective webpage
 - Deliverables and milestones:
 - EC recently started to send automatic reminders for deliverable submission

- The Project Office expects clear communication on the status of the deliverables and milestones well before the delivery date.
- Delays of > 2 months require an amendment
- The deliverable review process is defined in the deliverable template: <https://iagos-comm.iek.fz-juelich.de/dmsf/files/3609/view>
 - WP (co)leads are responsible to find reviewers)
 - The project office will send a reminder to find reviewers 10 weeks before delivery deadline
 - It was suggested to circulate a list of upcoming deliverables during the ENVRI weeks, in order to find committed reviewers; the project office will work on a procedure to find reviewers
- Reaching a milestone is documented by the respective means of verification, e.g. a short internal report and a brief statement which will be added to the project continuous reporting (EU Portal).
- EB members are asked to take requests for input from other WPs serious, as missing input or a considerable delay can risk the on-time submission of deliverables and milestones, as it happened already
- Project Office will try to modify Redmine emails to be more user-friendly
- **Letter of Support policy (Ari):**
 - It was agreed that the coordination team (Andreas and Ari) decides on request and justifies whether a LoS is provided, based on defined criteria (see meeting material 2.2), and whether ENVRI-FAIR or the ENVRI community (BEERi) should provide the LoS (BEERi LoS is more powerful than ENVRI-FAIR LoS)
 - First criterium should be changed to: “It benefits the goals of the ENVRI-FAIR project and jointly the ENVRI community aims.”
- **Data Management Plan update (Ari):**
 - Zenodo suggested as repository for project, as it also accepts non-public documents; uploaded documents have to be related to ENVRI community (managed by Ari), as done for ENVRI glossary (<https://zenodo.org/record/3465753#.XZx4FCDgpXk>)
 - Deliverables will be uploaded to Zenodo only after acceptance by EC (done by Project Office), they are available in Redmine after submission; authors of uploaded document are the deliverable authors
 - Project number has to be indicated in the Zenodo metadata; to avoid multiple DOIs in case of pre-prints, the metadata in Zenodo should clearly point to the actual publication
 - Suggested licence is CC4.0BY: The Project Office will check whether the EC has any constraints/ restrictions with regard to the licence
 - Solution for software licencing is pending
 - Software produced by RIs/ in subdomains are stored in RI repositories/ GitHub
 - Software produced within project should be open with a defined licence, access points are the RIs?
 - Solution should be defined in the DMP
 - Docker Hub: like GitHub but specifically for dockers
 - The data of individual RIs is RI business and not part of the ENVRI-FAIR DMP, however, the RI-specific DMPs should be harmonised to some level to be interoperable

3. Communications update (Magdalena)

- Website will be online mid of October

- EB members are asked to provide input for the ENVRI community session during ENVRI week in Feb 2020
- Amendment needed for D2.2, as it is based on the ENVRI strategy, which is not ready yet
- New illustrations available:
 - ENVRI community illustrations: Magdalena sent email today (2019-10-01), summarising the comments from RIs; there will also be a version with RI logos
 - Magdalena will share other illustrations soon and clarify how to cite them
 - When using/ modifying Daniele’s four-stages FAIR roadmap, cite the DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.3299353
(<https://zenodo.org/record/3299353#.XZyBECDgpXk>)
- EB members can contact Magdalena in case of any need for ENVRI-FAIR WP-specific communications material
- EB members are asked to upload any given presentation related to ENVRI-FAIR with a proper naming (optimal: name of presenter, short title of presentation, event, date) to Redmine: https://iagos-comm.iek.fz-juelich.de/projects/general-documents/dmsf?folder_id=217, as pdf and pptx files
- Upcoming meetings should be discussed in WP1-4 and EB meetings
- Alex commented that the internal part of the ENVRI-FAIR webpage should include a section with links to the most important Redmine folders
- Motto for ENVRI booth at GEOweek: “(FAIR) European hub to environmental (and Earth system) in-situ data” or similar
 - Paolo commented that we should have a strong message instead of understatements. Regarding “Environmental and Earth System” we said it would be wise to check the respective discussion during the ENVRI-FAIR preparation phase. There might be conflicts with the satellite community, but actually we state also “in-situ”.
 - Jacco commented that we actually need demonstrators
 - Paolo commented that the visions of GEO might not be the same as for ENVRI
- EGU 2020: proposal for Union Symposium failed, an ESSi session was proposed instead; there are some similar session proposed, the abstract and title of the session description can still be changed until 9th Oct.; Daniela will contact involved people
- The first external newsletter will come soon; short blog entries in the newsletter and longer articles on the webpage
 - EB members were asked to contribute, Ari and Andreas will provide a blog entry on other cluster projects and EOSC projects

4. Updates from WP3-11 and integrative aspects across WPs

a) WP3 (Paolo and Anca)

- Next BEERi meeting on 2019-11-27, most probably at Amsterdam airport:
 - EB members are asked to contact Anca to add topics to the agenda
 - ENVRI strategy will be discussed
- Election of the next BEERi chair:
 - Helen is in the election commission
 - The deadline for proposing candidates was moved to mid of October; there is one candidate so far; more suggestions are welcome.
- Anca is working on an overview of EOSC Development groups and EOSC-related projects and the responsible persons within the ENVRI-FAIR consortium, which might need to be redistributed (Meeting material 5.1)
 - 36 EOSC related projects right now, it is impossible to follow all of them, prioritisation by WP3 needed

- Anca requests reports from discussions with those groups and projects for D3.6 (report directly to Anca or add respective information into the travel reports) and to be involved more in respective activities by others
 - Anca is involved in project EOSC-Nordic
 - Anca will attend EOSC Symposium in Budapest
 - Participation in EOSC working groups (Zhiming, Cathrine, Alex)/ EOSC-hub Strategy Board (Andreas)
 - Request to move the organisation of first national stakeholder meeting (MS6) to M18, as it needs to be identified first who should be invited
 - Discuss in telcos; WPs to be included in this decision: Subdomains and WP4
 - Andreas in general requests more communication of WP3 with other WPs, e.g. in monthly WP1-4 telcos
- b) WP4 (Helen, Ari)**
- A consensus of FAIR policies between the RIs has to be created, the target is to have common policies with a minimum of RI-specific cases; this requires a different level of granularity for RI, subdomain and ENVRI community policies; one licence for the whole subdomain is not realisable.
 - Most important at this step is to bring together the right people: Membership in Policy working group (PWG) will be renewed, as the current composition is not progressing fast enough within the process of selecting RI policies
 - PWG needs to find out which policy changes have to be done, requires knowledge on which policies exist already; template needed for the assessment of the status quo; it needs to be decided whether a new policy survey is created or already existing material is used
 - Connections to other international communities exist: FAIRsFAIR Expert Group (Helen), FAIRsFAIR Policy Group (Ari)
- c) WP5 (Alex)**
- Ambition levels and plans differ widely between subdomains and RIs, which makes it challenging for WP5
 - Nominations from ENVRI for EOSC architecture WG should be done today (2019-10-01)
 - Training is needed especially on technology for smaller/ less mature RIs
 - Metadata standard identified as part of common gaps and priorities
 - Best practise workshops could be organised as combination of workshop and hackathon
 - WP5 review workshop (MS15): 2019-10-30 (Lund, more information at <https://sites.google.com/view/wp5workshop/home>)
 - Remote connection will be possible
 - One PWG member (WP4) should attend
 - Each subdomain has to be represented
 - WP5 is hoping for a common push forward by all RIs
 - RI data management systems are out of scope for marine domain?
 - E.g. Euro-Argo represents only 15-20 % of whole Argo, which makes it difficult to change the data management system on ENVRI-FAIR level
 - EOSC Early Adopter Programme (EAP): Zhiming has prepared a first draft (see Topic 5)
 - deadline for applications on 2019-10-15
 - funding for one year, services not for free anymore after that (will be also the case for EOSC services)
- d) WP6 (Jacco)**

- D6.1 represents a guidebook for further WP6 work
 - Training starts in M13, e.g., will be part of the ENVRI week agenda (Feb 2020)
 - Requirements need to be discussed with WP1 (incl. the target audience)
 - Use training material from Lecce FAIR training?
 - Feedback from WPs needed for Community Training Platform (CTP) design: Jacco will set up a respective task group; telco planned for next week with Magdalena
 - Jacco will send requests for milestone shifts to Daniela (part of the amendment)
 - Level of engagement from some of the sub-domains with WP6 PMs allocated has to be improved
 - Contact with training WPs of other ESFRI clusters exists, BUT: the focus of WP6 lies on the internal development for now, collaboration with others will follow later on
 - New EOSC WG on training will be launched soon; WP6 should contribute
- e) **WP7 (Zhiming)**
- The Knowledge Base (KB) is a collection of technological solutions from different RIs and currently in the prototype phase. WP7 will try to solve issues where no solution is available in the KB.
 - The progress in the different subdomains differs, hence, the deliverable timeline has to be adapted (subdomain development needs to be synchronised) to allow for harmonisation within WP5-7
 - Implementation plan roadmap will be discussed in WP5 review workshop
 - Draft implementation plans for the subdomains should be ready before the workshop
 - FAIR assessment as the starting point (input pending from WP10), followed by discussion on gap analysis, which is a precondition for the development of the technical implementation plan
- f) **WP8 (Cathrine)**
- D8.1 is drafted and will be circulated until 2019-10-15
 - MS34 (Existing policies and licences in use in the Atmospheric subdomain) could be important for selection of solutions
 - Progress workshop planned for Dec 2019 in Paris (also discussing licences on data and metadata)
 - Discussion needed on end-to-end demonstrators to serve EOSC expectations
- g) **WP9 (Thierry)**
- RIs are now working on D9.2, which will be submitted in M11; amendment needed for D9.6-9.8
- h) **WP10 (Garry and Daniele)**
- In the EPOS workshop (Sep 2019, Madrid) it turned out that the understanding of what is FAIR differs remarkably.
 - D10.1 is in risk of delay (activities need to speed up), since the harmonisation of implementation is challenging
 - We need an agreement on what is FAIR at least as kind of minimum consensus.
 - What do we want to offer researchers in the end?
 - How interoperable should it be?
 - Which bits of FAIR are we aiming for?
 - Implementation services to access the data?
 - We have not promised complete interoperability in the project, but some cases (demonstrators).
- i) **WP11 (Alberto)**
- Progress is a bit behind other subdomain WPs, however, D11.1 is planned on-time

- WP11 internal discussions on a booth/ workshop at the ESA (Ecological Society of America) conference in 2020 with focus on data
- Implementation plan meeting planned for Dec 2019

j) Integration across subdomains (Andreas)

- The design of the overall ENVRI-FAIR architecture requires the answer to the following questions:
 - Are we making interoperable central hubs and data repositories among all RIs in ENVRI-FAIR?
OR
 - Are we building a centralized ENVRI-FAIR hub interoperable with all hubs and RIs?
- The overall architecture of the hub should be decided before phrasing the strategy paper

Discussion:

- There was a general agreement that the complexity of a domain hub is too high.
 - A stepwise/ hierarchical approach is preferred, i.e. if interoperability exists on RI level, the interoperability on a higher level is not a problem.
 - RIs should have a certain level of interoperability within a subdomain.
 - Ari commented that another hub on top of RI hubs is actually not justifiable, but we need demonstrators to show that the hubs are interoperable and that we provide additional services through access to several interfaces.
 - Anca pointed out that we need to ask the researchers what they need.
 - EOVs and ECVs could be a proof of interoperability on subdomain level.
 - Interoperable services on top of subdomain level
 - Alex pointed out that solutions on subdomain level are problematic for multi-domain RIs.
- Andreas will circulate a draft for the ENVRI-FAIR EOSC position paper as input for discussion during the WP5 review workshop: start at bottom (1st option), multi-disciplinary layer in top (see: <https://iagos-comm.iek.fz-juelich.de/issues/1025>).
5. Approach towards other EOSC related projects and cluster projects/ EOSC statement paper an questionnaires/ Upcoming calls, proposals
- We did not have enough time to discuss the other topics. EOSC Development groups and cluster projects were mentioned in the WP3 report (see above, meeting material 5.1). Please see presentation 5.1 on some more information on EOSC cluster projects and meeting material 5.2 for information on upcoming calls and proposals.
 - Zhiming has drafted an application for the EOSC-hub Early Adopter Programme (see meeting material 5.3) and kindly asks for comments (see also: <https://iagos-comm.iek.fz-juelich.de/issues/1017>).
6. Planning of the ENVRI week in Feb 2020
- The first ENVRI week will take place on 3-7 Feb 2020 in Hotel Elbflorenz in Dresden.
 - We have quickly discussed the agenda and some suggestions were made, e.g. to include a technical workshop (for technical personnel) on Thursday and to move the Friday afternoon slot for BEERi to Thursday after lunch.
 - EB members are requested to share their comments on the agenda and requirements for sessions in the following Redmine issue: <https://iagos-comm.iek.fz-juelich.de/issues/1022>.
7. Amendment and budget reallocations
- We did not have enough time to discuss this topic. Please see meeting material 7 for some information. Daniela is in contact with all relevant people. The amendment will be

submitted at the latest in November after discussing the adaptations of the deliverables during the WP5 review workshop on 2019-10-30.

8. Overview on EB-related structure and functionalities in Redmine
 - We did not have enough time to talk about this topic. Links to important Redmine folders are given in the EB report replacing the 2nd EB meeting (meeting material 2.1).
 - We moved the working environment of the ENVRI glossary to Redmine (as the EGI confluence will not be continued): <https://iagos-comm.iek.fz-juelich.de/projects/envri-fair-wiki/wiki>. The glossary is publicly available, but can be modified only by certain managers. Daniela will soon create a Redmine issue asking the WP leads to announce those people in the WP who should be managers of this working environment. The current status of the glossaries is uploaded to Zenodo under one DOI (<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3465753>) and will be updated regularly based on its development in the Redmine working environment. The following DOI will always resolve the latest version of the glossary.
9. Next EB meeting (2019-12-03, virtual)
 - The next EB meeting will be held virtually on 2019-12-03. The Project Office further suggests to have a lunch-to-lunch meeting in spring 2020 in preparation of the first periodic report (M18 = Jun 2020) and the midterm project review (M22 = Oct 2020).
10. AOB
 - Proposal for publishing Annex 1 of the GA (non-confidential contents):
We did not have enough time to discuss this topic. Daniela will prepare a respective request for decision by the EB.

11. Decisions

1. The two new WP6 co-leads (Jacco Konijn and Nicola Fiore) are accepted for the EB without any objection. The rearrangement will be subject to final approval by the next GA.
2. The coordination team (Andreas and Ari) decides on request and justifies whether a LoS is provided, based on defined criteria, and whether ENVRI-FAIR or the ENVRI community (BEERi) should provide the LoS. In addition, the first criterium should be changed to: “It benefits the goals of the ENVRI-FAIR project and jointly the ENVRI community aims.”

12. Action items

Agenda Item	Action	Responsibility	Due date
2	• Provide reports on communications actions (travel reports) for past and upcoming events/ meetings > Provide example travel reports	all Andreas/ Ari all	Ongoing 2019-10-31 Ongoing
	• Check for the latest version in Redmine whenever using a template or overview presentation	all	Ongoing
	• Share any information of past and upcoming ENVRI-FAIR relevant meetings, events and deadlines with Daniela	all	Ongoing
	• Clearly communicate towards the Project Office on the status of the deliverables and milestones well before the delivery date	Project Office	Ongoing
	• Send reminders for deliverable review process 10 weeks ahead of the delivery data	Project Office Project Office Project Office Project Office	2019-10-31 2019-10-31 2019-10-31 2019-10-25
	• Work on a procedure to find reviewers		

Agenda Item	Action	Responsibility	Due date
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Try to modify Redmine emails to be more user-friendly Prepare LoS template Check whether the EC has any constraints/ restrictions with regard to the licencing of project documents (e.g., deliverables) 		
3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Input for the ENVRI community session during ENVRI week in Feb 2020 to Magdalena Feedback on Power Point template to Magdalena Upload any given presentation related to ENVRI-FAIR with a proper naming to Redmine Modify EGU 2020 ESSI session proposal Provide short entries for first external newsletter to Magdalena <ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Provide a blog entry on other cluster projects and EOSC projects 	all all all Project Office all Andreas/ Ari	2019-10-25 2019-10-15 Ongoing 2019-10-09 2019-10-31 2019-10-31
4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Contact Anca to add topics to the agenda of the BEERi meeting on 2019-11-27 Provide reports of discussions with EOSC development groups/ cluster projects to Anca Contact Helen to suggest new BEERi chair Prioritise EOSC Development groups and EOSC-related projects (which ones to follow) Register for the WP5 review workshop in case of interest Discuss on Community Training Platform (CTP) design and set up a task group Send requests for milestone shifts to Daniela Input for WP5 review workshop Circulate a draft for ENVRI-FAIR EOSC position document as input for discussion during the WP5 review workshop 	all all all WP3 all Jacco/ Magdalena Jacco/ Paolo WP10 Andreas	2019-10-31 Ongoing 2019-10-15 2019-11-15 2019-10-21 2019-10-31 2019-10-15 2019-10-20 2019-10-05
5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Comment on Zhiming's application draft for EOSC-hub EAP 	all	2019-10-14
6	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Comment ENVRI week agenda and send requirements for sessions to Daniela 	all	2019-10-08
9	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Organize EB lunch-to-lunch meeting for spring 2020 	Project Office	By the end of 2019
10	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Prepare a request for decision by the EB to publish Annex 1 of the GA (non-confidential contents) 	Project Office	2019-10-18

4.4 4th EB meeting, 3 December 2019, virtual

Meeting minutes

1. Approval of agenda
 - The agenda was approved by the EB.
2. Update by the Project Office
 - **Reporting period I:**
 - The Project Office announced the upcoming end of project reporting period I in M18 and a related timeline. More information/ instructions will follow in the next months.
 - Magdalena and Helen mentioned that an external audit is only necessary for the final periodic report (for partners with contributions from 325.000 € without indirect costs).
 - WP9 would like to organise the preparation of the WP9 technical report differently than suggested, in a way that WP9 writes the report from scratch without the preparatory work of the partners. The goal is to have a more efficient preparation of a more coherent report. However, Magdalena pointed out that the preparatory work by the partners is relevant for the Project Office in order to understand the justification of costs. Addressing this issue, Sylvie suggested to have clear instructions by the Project office which information is needed.
 - Sanna reported that in ACTRIS a table-based template developed by EPOS is used and recommends to use this as well in ENVRI-FAIR. She will share the template with the EB/ Project Office. The template could be spread by the WP leads to the respective partners or centrally by the Project office.
 - Andreas suggested that the Project office will work on the development of a procedure and to present and fix it at the ENVRI week in February.
 - Juanjo pointed out that the information “The EC requests justifications for PMs strongly deviating from the DoA” has to be more precise. The Project Office will give respective information in the next months.
 - **Deliverables and milestones:**
 - D4.2 will be delayed to M14 or M15, as WP4 plans to restructure the PWG. The other WPs (esp. subdomains) will be involved soon. It was suggested to use the ENVRI week to receive input for this deliverable or, alternatively, to present the outcome of the analysis and to get final comments. This could be part of the GA (in order to have a broad audience), a minimum of 30 min would be needed.
 - D5.1 is in work. Alex convinced Barbara to not go too deep into detail, nevertheless, the deliverable might be submitted in January. Andreas mentioned that he agreed with Barbara that detailed subdomain information will be placed in the Appendix, which is not uploaded as official part of the deliverable to the EU portal but will be stored in Redmine for internal use.
 - D10.1 has been sent to the reviewer, WP10 expects the final version to be sent to the Project Office before the Christmas holidays.
 - D11.1 might be a bit delayed as one of the RIs (LifeWatch ERIC) will provide the input during this week only. Alberto expects to have a draft in December, which, however, needs to go through the review.
 - D9.3 is expected on time in M15. The respective template will be to the RIs in December.
 - MS6 will be delayed. For May 2020 a one-day event is planned in Brussels where two WP3 milestones will be served: MS6 and MS7. Sanna suggested to move MS6 to M17. MS7 is due in M18. Magdalena offered to help with the promotion of the event.
 - Helen suggested to move MS12 to M16 so that WP4 can include the outcome of the discussion at the GA during the ENVRI week in February.
 - Amendment:

- The Project Office informed the EB members that information on the amendment was sent to the GA on 2019-12-02 for approval.

3. Communications update

- Magdalena reported on the progress within WP2 (see slides) and asked everyone to:
 - use the newest version of the power point template available in Redmine (https://iagos-comm.iek.fz-juelich.de/projects/general-documents/dmsf?folder_id=227)
 - provide input for the WP2 dissemination work, e.g. to write travel reports (template available in Redmine: https://iagos-comm.iek.fz-juelich.de/projects/task-2-1-development-and-implementation-of-the-envri-fair-communication-strategy/dmsf?folder_id=286) and to add events and meetings to the event and meeting calendar including the name of the person who is attending (<https://iagos-comm.iek.fz-juelich.de/projects/contact-information/issues>)
 - let her know about any need for help in promoting events and developing dissemination material
 - inform her about new RIs and initiatives in the environmental domain, to be invited to the ENVRI community session during the ENVRI week (agenda can be found here: <https://iagos-comm.iek.fz-juelich.de/dmsf/files/3935/view>)
 - provide input for the next newsletter today
- Alberto asked whether Magdalena has already continued the networking with communications specialists of the RIs as started in ENVRIplus. Magdalena said they are receiving already the newsletter and they will together work soon on a joint communications strategy in view of the joint booth at EGU 2020.

4. Conclusions of WP5 workshop

- Alex reported on the outcomes of the WP5 workshop in Lund (2019-10-30, see slides).
- There seems to be a tendency in the RIs, that they are motivated to go beyond FAIR and to address also data use. It was concluded that within the project we should not lose track of the actual objectives.
- Six cross-cutting task forces (TF) were initiated (see https://iagos-comm.iek.fz-juelich.de/projects/wp-5-common-requirements-and-testbed-for-meta-data-services-community-standards-and-cataloguing/wiki/WP5_task_forces), inspired by the EOSC TFs. People interested in the TFs are asked to add their name to the group list (<https://fileshare.icos-cp.eu/apps/onlyoffice/s/jGXNiCBpdFo7KJj>) by end of this week (2019-12-08). Each TF should have one or more specialists of WP7, (WP5, WP4) plus at least one per interested RI, specialists from EOSC where and when relevant.
- Zhiming asked about the distinction between TF “User-oriented cross-domain demonstration cases” and Task 7.4 (WP7). Andreas stated that the idea for this TF came from the point that at the end of the project we need science-driven results, not only technology-driven results, and agreed that the expectations to both of them has to be clarified.
- Sanna promised stronger support for WP5 activities in the future, as one data scientist will be hired by FMI from January 2020.

5. Updates from WP3, WP4 and WP6

k) WP3:

- Sanna reported on the progress within WP3. For May 2020 a one-day event is planned in Brussels where three WP6 tasks and two milestones will be served: Tasks 3.1, 3.3 and 3.4; MS6 and MS7. The event will have three sessions:
 - ENVRI-FAIR and the connection with national stakeholders
 - ENVRI and the international collaboration (with data hubs and how the RIs are connected to GEO, COPERNICUS, EOSC)

- iii. Innovation – cooperation with industry
 - Anca reported on Task 3.2. She was recently attending the RDA 14th Plenary (Oct) in Helsinki and the EOSC Symposium and Coordination Day in Budapest (Nov). At the Coordination Day ENVRI-FAIR was the only cluster project attending. The main outcome was the creation of five interest groups. Anca will share the minutes as soon as they are available. The EOSC landscape appears to be very fragmented, keeping all involved people busy.
 - For Task 3.4 work will start now, the contribution by other partners will be needed.
 - To avoid potential duplication of work, Maggie mentioned that OpenAIRE offers webinars on legal aspects of data-driven innovation.
 - l) **WP4:**
 - Ari reported on the progress within WP4, where the PWG is currently restructured as discussed in the last EB meeting.
 - m) **WP6:**
 - Maggie reported on the progress within WP6 (see slides). The beta version of the Common Training Platform will be launched beginning of 2020 and presented during the ENVRI week in Feb 2020, where also the first f2f training event will be offered. A summer school will be organised in autumn 2020.
 - WP6 is organizing a webinar on the resource "FAIRsharing.org" on 13th December. Everyone in the ENVRI-FAIR community is welcome to attend it. WP6 particularly asks for the representation of all RIs involved in ENVRI-FAIR in the audience. More information: <https://iagos-comm.iek.fz-juelich.de/issues/1129>.
6. Planning of the ENVRI week in Feb.
- Daniela presented the current version of the agenda, requesting feedback from the EB members in this issue generated after the meeting: <https://iagos-comm.iek.fz-juelich.de/issues/1139>.
 - It was agreed that the TF sessions should be open for everyone. Daniela will contact the TF leads to discuss the optimal format for the sessions. Alex denied the necessity of a WP5 working session in addition to the TF sessions.
 - Sylvie criticised that WP8-11 do not have any session to inform each other on the progress. It was agreed that this should replace the TF Introductory talks on Tuesday.
 - Sanna and Helen agreed to give a talk in the Plenary session on Monday. It was agreed that a coordinated approach will be needed to avoid any duplication in the talks.
 - Magdalena pointed out that the best way to book a hotel room is to call or send an email to the hotel (https://www.hotel-elbflorenz.de/hotels_dresden_kontakt.aspx) (instead of using the online booking system), to make sure you will get the agreed price (refer to "ENVRI-FAIR").
7. Strategy
- **INFRAEOSC-03 call:**
 - Andreas reported from the EOSC Symposium in Budapest, where he met the coordinators of the other cluster projects. There, they presented their joint statement towards the European Commission (EC) on the INFRAEOSC-03 call. This call is important with 40 Mio € budget. Only one proposal is expected from the clusters, but detailed expectations are not communicated by the EC towards the clusters. The clusters agreed that either all clusters are participating equally to the proposal, using their synergies, or there will not be a single proposal. The EC also expects only a limited number of partners in the proposal. Until 15th Dec. all cluster consortia will decide on the respective partners being involved. For each cluster a successful proposal would bring 1-2 full positions.

- Andreas asked the EB to decide on the internal process in this regard. It was decided that Andreas as coordinator stays the main contact in this matter for ENVRI-FAIR and short-cuts with the individual WPs when needed, as quick responses are needed (proposal deadline is end of March 2020). He will regularly inform the EB on the progress. Alex recommended to start with the resource planning.
 - The next meeting with the other clusters will take place on 2020-01-10 in Brussels.
 - **ENVRI-FAIR Position Paper on the EOSC:**
 - Andreas reported on regular meetings with the other clusters in the framework of the EOSC-Hub Strategy Board. The clusters decided to use a common template for their position papers towards the EOSC, which will then be used by the EOSC Secretariat to formulate a summary. The material developed will be useful for any statements of the clusters on their relation to the EOSC. In the paper, the topic sustainability plays an important role. The requirements table was taken from the EOSC Federating Core Community Position Paper.
 - Andreas asks for feedback for the already advanced draft (link to the document is available here: https://iagos-comm.iek.fz-juelich.de/projects/envri-fair-executive-board/wiki/Working_draft_2019-12-03) until 2019-12-10. He will finalise the paper during next week and will consider the paper accepted after the feedback. No major objections were communicated either during the BEERi on 2019-11-27. Maggie pointed out that it would be very beneficial to have the authors mentioned on the papers to gain more credibility. In case of the Position paper Andreas and Ari will be the main authors.
 - No other recent/ upcoming calls and consultations were discussed.
8. Proposal for an annual feedback round on collaboration between the WPs
- Daniela presented a proposal to introduce a feedback round on the cooperation between the ENVRI-FAIR WPs, which would be repeated annually and conducted either in the form of a standardised anonymous survey or bilateral talks. The second option would be preferred by the EB members, e.g. as 15 min talks during the ENVRI week. Maggie suggested to have a need-based feedback procedure only.
9. Election of new EB chair
- Cathrine Lund Myhre (Atmospheric subdomain) was proposed and accepted as EB chair for the second project year (2020). This election has to be approved by the GA in the next meeting.
10. Next EB meeting and Lunch-to-lunch meeting
- **Next EB meeting:**
 - The next EB meeting will take place during the ENVRI week in Dresden, 2020-02-05.
 - **Lunch-to-lunch meeting:**
 - A lunch-to-lunch EB meeting is planned for spring 2020 at Burg Obbendorf (close to Forschungszentrum Jülich, Germany). The idea of this meeting is to discuss strategic aspects, particularly what exactly we want to have reached at the end of ENVRI-FAIR, and to start preparations for the mid-term review meeting. Two international airports (Cologne/ Bonn and Düsseldorf) are close to the suggested venue. Transportation from those airports to the venue can be arranged. The Project Office would like to encourage all WP leads and co-leads to attend this additional meeting with one overnight stay in order to have focused discussions on "broader" strategic topics and the preparation of the midterm review without being "disturbed" by the typical necessities during regular one-day EB meetings.

- The poll to find the optimal date for the meeting is available here: <https://terminplaner4.dfn.de/bciMqAepDZCDiefT>. Daniela asked everyone to answer it until 2019-12-06.

11. AOB

12. Maggie suggested to have a similar list for deliverables as existing for milestones (<https://iagos-comm.iek.fz-juelich.de/dmsf/files/3937/view>) on Redmine. Daniela will implement this. **Decisions**

1. Cathrine Lund Myhre (Atmospheric subdomain) was accepted as EB chair for the second project year (2020)

13. Action items

Agenda Item	Action	Responsibility	Due date
2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Share table-based technical report template developed by EPOS • Share information and work on the development of a procedure for the first periodic reporting and present and fix it at the ENVRI week in February 	Sanna Project Office	asap 2020-02-03
3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • use the newest version of the power point template available in Redmine • provide input for the WP2 dissemination work, e.g. to write travel reports and to add events and meetings to the event and meeting calendar including the name of the person who is attending • let Magdalena know about any need for help in promoting events and developing dissemination material • inform her about new RIs and initiatives in the environmental domain, to be invited to the ENVRI community session during the ENVRI week 	All	ongoing
4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clarify expectations to TF on demonstration cases and Task 7.4 	Andreas, Zhiming, and others	asap
6	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Comment on ENVRI week agenda • Register and book hotel rooms • Work on agenda 	All All Project Office	2019-12-06 2019-12-05 2019-12-11
7	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide feedback for the Position paper draft 	All	2019-12-10
8	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Work on feedback procedure 	Project Office	2020-02-03
10	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fill poll for lunch-to-lunch EB meeting 	All	2019-12-10

4.5 5th EB meeting, 5 February 2020, Dresden, DE

Meeting minutes

1. Approval of agenda
 - The agenda was approved by the EB.
 - Additional items for the AOB section:

- Collaboration with other clusters (Magdalena)

2. Update by the Project Office

- **Deliverables:**
 - The request to postpone D4.2 to M14 or M15 was confirmed again by Helen.
 - Postponing of D2.2 and D9.6 are approved by EC Project Officer.
 - D5.1, D8.2 and D11.1 are expected in M14 (Barbara shared draft of D5.1 the same day).
- **Milestones:**
 - MS22, MS23 and MS66 are pending. Garry promised to share with the PO what he has for MS66.
 - Planning of:
 - **Strategy Meeting**
 - Andreas explained the focus of the Strategy meeting:
 - What will be the ENVR-Hhub? (This is an ongoing discussion, e.g., in WP5 meetings)
 - Preparation of the mid-term review
 - It was discussed if the meeting could be shifted in time, as there is an overlap with the RDA Plenary in Melbourne and the RI conference in Zagreb. It was further commented that the flights are already very expensive and the venue is difficult to reach, although the PO would offer a pick-up service.
 - In the end it was decided to have a lunch-to-lunch meeting instead in Amsterdam from 7th to 8th April 2020. Zhiming and Jacco will organise a room and provide suggestions for hotels. Andreas confirmed that budget is available for room rent if needed. PO will cancel booking at Burg Obbendorf.
 - **Reporting period I:**
 - Daniela has modified the timeline according to the suggestion in the GA meeting to shift the whole procedure by two weeks. This timeline was agreed.
 - **Midterm review**
 - EU Project Officer suggested to prepare it along WPs instead along partners
- **Amendment 2:**
 - The potential case for an amendment by UKRI/ CEH was withdrawn by Helen, as there is no budget that can be shifted to CEH.
 - Magdalena announced request to postpone D2.2 (which is postponed already to M24) even further, as the ENVRI strategy, on which D2.2 will build on, will not be finished in near future. This case does not need an amendment, but we would need the approval by the EC Project Officer.

3. Updates from WP3, WP4, WP5, WP7

- **WP3:**
 - Work currently focussed on preparation of the one-day high-level workshop in Brussels, which will most probably take place in June. The workshop will cover two milestones (MS6 and MS7) and will have three sessions:
 - ENVRI-FAIR and the connection with national stakeholders (with representatives of different countries and RIs)
 - ENVRI and the international collaboration (with data hubs and how the RIs are connected to GEO, COPERNICUS, EOSC)
 - Innovation – cooperation with industry
Input is planned from, e.g., the European Commission, ESFRI and Andreas for ENVRI-FAIR. Priorities are now to fix the date for the workshop, to book a venue and to invite the speakers. Magdalena offered to provide national contact points.
 - Jacco commented that we need a clear strategy how to approach GEO. The question was raised if this is the duty of BEERi.
- **WP4:**
 - WP4 is working with WP5 review workshop outcomes and restructuring the Policy working group (PWG). The target is to have those people of the RIs in the PWG, which work closely with policies and licences and to get these new members up to speed now. Two PWG working session were scheduled during ENVRI week, plus an open policy

landscape discussion. The goal was to gain a better understanding of the policy landscape and how to engage with the RIs. The PWG membership remains an open issue, as less people than invited joined the sessions.

- **WP5:**
 - WP5 is finishing D5.1 and coming back to the FAIRness assessment, whereby WP5 will follow/ co-develop the work of GO-FAIR on a new version. The next assessment is planned for April 2021, the third assessment at the end of the project. As the method will change, the two upcoming assessments will not be directly comparable to the first assessment in 2019.
 - Alex reported that all subdomains have prepared implementation plans and that the task forces started their work, which is followed by WP5. Task force F2F meetings are scheduled for the ENVRI weeks only, but there are monthly telcos between the task force leads and WP5. Alex will report on the progress in the task forces within the EB meetings.
- **WP7:**
 - WP7 is currently digesting the outputs of WP5 work and feeding the knowledge base, which was internally launched. So far it consists of three contents: results of previous projects, a service portfolio and the results of the first FAIRness assessment.
 - WP7 is working on a common development plan.
 - The application for the Early Adopter Programme has entered the 2nd phase.

4. Participation to INFRAEOSC-03 call, ESFRI RI conference, workshop organised by ESFRI

- **Participation to INFRAEOSC-03 call (Ari):**
 - The call is a kind of intermediate station between H2020 and the EOSC-hub.
 - During a workshop organised by Technopolis, who is coordinating the proposal, it was discussed how the budget will be distributed (and thereby how much of the budget will go to the clusters). It was agreed that each cluster can have up to three partners involved in the proposal.
 - Ari showed the list of tasks in which the clusters are expected to contribute or take the lead. The clusters are asked to indicate the budget for those. It is strategically important to contribute in specific tasks.
 - The three potential contributors per cluster need to be communicated to Technopolis this week. Mainly senior positions are expected. They will need to report back to the respective clusters.
 - The following suggestions came up during the EB meeting:
 - Dick Schaap (SeaDataNet) might be interested (Sylvie will contact him)
 - More mature RIs should be involved, e.g., EPOS? (Helen will ask Massimo)
 - Alberto will discuss within LifeWatch ERIC
 - Alex might have one person which could contribute (ICOS ERIC)
 - Ari will share the list of tasks with Alex, Sylvie and Alberto.
 - Technopolis would prefer that the clusters provide less partners but more Linked third parties, subcontractors. This offers the chance to rearrange the work later.
- **ESFRI RI conference (Andreas):**
 - It is in the responsibility of the RIs to participate. The overlap with the EB strategy meeting is solved.
- **Workshop organised by ESFRI (Andreas):**
 - Second ESFRI Workshop on RIs and EOSC (13-14 May 2020 in Dubrovnik, Croatia)
 - The first workshop was organised in London in 2019.
 - Andreas asked to save the date! There might be expectations towards the clusters to demonstrate what the EOSC will be. We should start thinking about this.

5. 5. Other upcoming events, workshops, conferences etc. related to EOSC

- Jacco asked to forward information on upcoming events related to training to him.
- EOSC lists upcoming events on their webpage.

6. AOB

- **Collaboration with other clusters** (Magdalena):
 - Magdalena joins regular calls between the communications experts of all clusters. They have started a table with contacts for different tasks, which are of relevance for all clusters, in order to connect those people.
 - Magdalena asked EB members to go through the following document and to enter the contact person within ENVRI-FAIR for each task until Friday:
<https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1vSLhxTEgLYyXSqtA1LDnbnANKHY1vLRaYea2ZEZOSgw/edit#gid=0>
- **Task Force 1 (AAI) (Alex):**
 - All RIs are interested in working together on this topic. The EB should provide support. It has to be decided by the RIs if a centralised or federated hub is preferred. Implementation is planned for the end of this year.
- **Information about BEERi meeting outcomes** (Cathrine):
 - Cathrine came back to the comment of Ulpu earlier that week (communications session) that BEERi meeting outcomes might be communicated openly in the future and suggested that the EB is announcing its support for this change. The decision will be made in the BEERi meeting on Thursday/ Friday.
- **Coverage of costs for WP activities (e.g., during ENVRI weeks) by WP1 (Daniela):**
 - Andreas stated that this will be decided in consultation with the respective WPs.

7. Action items

Agenda Item	Action	Responsibility	Due date
2	Organise a room and provide suggestions for hotels in Amsterdam for EB Strategy meeting	Zhiming, Jacco	2020-02-29 (?)
	Cancel booking at Burg Obbendorf	Project Office	2020-02-07
4	Discuss about involvement in INFRAEOSC-03 proposal	Sylvie (will contact Dick, SeaDataNet), Alex within ICOS ERIC, Alberto within LifeWatch ERIC	2020-02-09
6	Go through the following document and to enter the contact person within ENVRI-FAIR for each task until Friday: https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1vSLhxTEgLYyXSqtA1LDnbnANKHY1vLRaYea2ZEZOSgw/edit#gid=0	All	2020-02-07

4.6 EB Strategy meeting, 7 April 2020, virtual

Meeting minutes

INTRODUCTION

Introduction of the agenda was given in which it was stressed that the focus of the strategy meeting should be put on the definition of the ENVRI-FAIR goals and the kind of services delivered to EOSC. One major outcome of the strategy meeting will be an internal report on the ENVRI-Hub architecture, similar to the report on the WP5 Review Workshop held at Lund University on 30 October 2019 (MS15 Report). The project management team is responsible for the preparation of this report. In the following, the topics refer to the agenda items and include the links to the presentations.

1. TOPIC 1 Setting the frame – expectations of ENVRI-FAIR goals (Andreas)

Main conclusions of the presentation are:

- As stated by the ESFRI Working Group on EOSC, sharing open data should be one of the major services of EOSC, and the Science Clusters (EOSC-Life, ENVRI-FAIR, SSHOC, ESCAPE and PANOSC) are seen as key providers of content to EOSC.
- Cross-domain demonstration cases and services are requested as key output of ENVRI-FAIR for EOSC.
- ENVRI-Hub functionalities should include
 - (1) access to data provided by ENVRIIs,
 - (2) access to services and products provided by ENVRIIs,
 - (3) facilities for cross-domain search, and
 - (4) access to thematic services of research infrastructures.

In the discussion the question came up, who are the users of the services and who are the service providers. Overall the Science Clusters are considered first class citizens of EOSC, highlighting their important role. From the RI perspective, RIs may act as service providers when providing content (data, scientific services) to the EOSC, and act as users, when using EOSC services. From e-Infrastructure perspective, EOSC-hub is seen as service provider and RIs are seen as users. These questions will finally be answered by the rules of participation to EOSC.

Another open question concerns the definition of data products and services. By now, there is no coherent definition among the RIs participating in ENVRI-FAIR. It was agreed that ENVRI-FAIR should work towards a common understanding among the participating RIs of data products and data services. This item will become one part of the internal report on the ENVRI-Hub architecture.

A first round of the discussion focused on the ENVRI-Hub which was then discussed further in TOPIC 2:

- Most of the participants understand that the ENVRI-Hub will be implemented on top of the existing RI portals and access interfaces and serve as a common portal to the data of the contributing RIs.
- The ENVRI-Hub will serve as a complementary access path to the RI data products and services.
- The design of the ENVRI catalogue of services will be developed by Task Force 1 (TF1); currently TF1 aims at Web-APIs for access to make the ENVRI data assets also FAIR to machines.
- Developing a GUI with options for faceted search and cross-domain search seems desirable, but might be too complex to achieve in the duration of the project; we should be cautious with our ambitions.
- The GUI in particular needs to be discussed with the high-level RI representatives since it impacts directly the internet presence and visibility of the individual RIs.
- It seems appropriate to establish a Task Force dedicated to the design of the ENVRI-Hub; it was suggested that Task Force 6 should take over this action.

2. TOPIC 2 ENVRI-Hub – concept and content (Alex, Zhiming)

Main conclusions are: The ENVRI-Hub concept is depending on the EOSC environment which is continuously changing. More reliable information may be available from the INFRAEOSC-03 project which is currently in preparation. One potential role of ENVRI-Hub would be to serve as EOSC Interoperability Framework.

In the discussion, it was commented that providing a catalogue of services is doable as this relies on the prepared catalogue by TF1. However, providing cross-domain search capabilities would mean an enormous amount of work on metadata (see also discussion to TOPIC 1). Examples for cross-domain searches are given on the EOSC portal, but we have to check if they are useful or not, and worth the effort.

It was suggested to have not only an API but also a portal to show visibility to users. However, setting up a proper functioning and useable portal takes another 4 years and may see delays. Providing a portal might be too complex and instead we may do a feasibility study on the potential functionalities of ENVRI-Hub. In general, the development of a portal or a GUI should involve the contributing RIs on the senior level.

The benefit of a GUI to the users is discussed controversially. One position claims that an ENVRI portal is useless, since users who want to access RI data go directly to the RI portal. The other position says that it is necessary to have the different viewpoints of different users in mind, i.e., different users -> different starting points -> different access interfaces (portals).

In summary:

- There is no hub promised in the proposal, instead we want to lay the foundations for an access interface.
- TF1 is working on the service catalogue, including data, metadata and data services exposable to EOSC.
- ENVRI-Hub will complement the efforts on RI level and serve as an access layer connecting the RIs and subdomains.
- We should strive for a federated search.
- The feasibility of a portal / hub should be studied, that work can be organised by TF6.
- A GUI is needed for visibility. The GUI has to be discussed in detail also with the RIs. It was not promised to have this running at the end of the project.
- The major goal of ENVRI-FAIR is the accessibility of data and services, but not how far we will go for the science driven services.

3. TOPIC 3 Statements by Subdomains on their plans about the final products delivered to EOSC

3.1 **Atmosphere** (WP8 Catherine / Damien)

The approach of the Atmosphere subdomain is to start from the services developed at RI level, to map these services provided by the RIs as the basis for the ENVRI-FAIR service catalogue and continue from here for further development of the service catalogue exposed to EOSC. One potential focus could be on satellite data.

Clarification is requested on what type of products/services ENVRI-FAIR would like to expose strategically.

3.2 **Marine** (WP9 Thierry)

The Marine subdomain is focusing on the development of data and metadata APIs based on standards and search engine APIs for cross domain activities. The presented workflow can be implemented when the data APIs which each RI is developing become available. Task 9.8 (Demonstration: query and subset Essential Ocean Variables across Marine RIs) will be the first users of the API. Possibly extend the demonstration with TF6 to ENVRI-FAIR RIs.

The presented workflow is roughly the same as was developed in EPOS, but without EOSC. It works among marine RIs, but could go further. It was discussed if the workflow is already applicable to the other subdomains, especially atmosphere.

3.3 **Solid Earth** (WP10 Keith)

A ranking for the options for the appropriate interface between ENVRI and EOSC would be:

- 1) ENVRI-Hub acts like AMAZON as a simple interface to the EOSC.
- 2) ENVRI-Hub offers harmonized catalogues of RIs: requests by users can be processed on the computing nodes of the individual RIs, if relevant data can be updated frequently enough; ENVRI-Hub serves as a moderator between users and subdomains or single RIs.
- 3) Streaming ENVRI data to the EOSC (putting ENVRI into EOSC as a whole) would be the most advanced option, but we are losing management power that way since we have no monitoring of data use.

One clear recommendation is to use a minimum number of interfaces. In that respect it needs to be clarified whether the ENVRI-Hub is needed and what its role would be, and in particular what the content of a minimum viable ENVRI-Hub should be.

3.4 **Biodiversity and Ecosystems** (WP11 Alberto)

Each RI has developed its plan for improving FAIRness of data resources and services. Data resources, services and VREs will be made available for the harvesting by EOSC through FAIR catalogues by every RI.

Biodiversity and Ecosystems RIs' integrated services will build on RI level services and include show cases on specific research topics dealing with biodiversity and ecosystems status, conservation, and recovery.

Biodiversity and Ecosystems subdomain has a workflow similar to the Marine and Solid Earth subdomains implemented since LifeWatch as coordinating RI is not committed to collecting data but is an e-Infrastructure by itself.

4. TOPIC 4 Plans of related ESFRI Cluster projects

4.1 **EOSC – Life** (life sciences, Ari)

EOSC-Life overall objective is to build an open collaborative space for digital biology in Europe. Steps taken include

- Establish EOSC-Life by publishing FAIR life science data resources in EOSC & establish the policies needed for access
- Create an ecosystem of innovative life-science tools in EOSC & connect them to users via a shared single login system
- Enable ground-breaking data driven research in Europe by connecting life scientists to interoperable

European clouds via open calls for participation EOSC-Life concentrates on interoperability aspects, including workflow engines, common AAI and provenance. Here, technical challenges are similar to ENVRI-FAIR and close collaboration on these levels is suggested.

Main tools are connected to open pilot use cases.

4.2 SSHOC (social sciences and humanities, Andreas)

Postponed more in-depth information requested from SSHOC.

5. TOPIC 5 Discussion and agreement on ENVRI-FAIR goals and ENVRI-Hub concept and content

Summary of the discussion so far (by Andreas):

- **FAIRness of ENVRI data:** ENVRI-Hub is the test case if we succeeded to make the RIs more FAIR, see also the requirements stated in TOPIC 1.
- **ENVRI-FAIR necessity:** We try to attract different type of users outside of our specific research communities. These are mainly interdisciplinary users, who are not coming from the RIs and not from the EOSC side. ENVRI-Hub should offer easy and moderate access to RI resources. If we accept this task as on our table, ENVRI-Hub is needed.
- **ENVRI-Hub functionalities:** All the functionality of ENVRI-Hub will be provided by EOSC. The main role of ENVRI-Hub is to moderate the interactive processes between users and subdomains or single RIs.
- **EOSC-Life approach:** EOSC-Life has chosen the approach to develop a VRE build on an open collaborative space for digital biology in Europe, is this also an option for ENVRI-FAIR?

Discussion on functionalities of ENVRI-Hub and resulting structure:

- Interoperability is necessary.
- Technically the architecture and functionalities of ENVRI-Hub will be driven by the applications, or use cases and user needs, respectively.
- If there is a demand for ENVRI-Hub and specific functionalities we are motivated to provide them.
- We should use “Use cases” top down to design the ENVRI-Hub. We can develop science driven cases to define the requirements, but don’t need to make them work. The use case definition bridges to the activities in INFRAEOSC-03.
- Use cases should be designed along cross-subdomain science questions like, e.g. interaction of air pollution, climate change and spreading of diseases (see use cases for INFRAEOSC-03 WP6).

Main challenge is to fit the different pieces (Catalogue, ENVRI-Hub) together since the involved pieces do not converge naturally into a common goal. So the goals need to be adjusted. It was agreed that this task should be taken up by TF6 in an ENVRI-Hub design study. Also the design of the catalogue has to be part of this study.

In the subdomains we see broad “diversity” of approaches and goals, driven by user requirements. Therefore, we have to focus the activities towards the ENVRI-Hub goal. Until summer we have to revisit the work plans of the subdomains to match the ENVRI-Hub goal and make on use cases.

As said before. TF6 will be the place, i.e., TF6 will keep its portfolio and ENVRI-Hub becomes part of it.

6. TOPIC 6 Miscellaneous: INFRAEOSC-07 call

Postponed to next meeting

7. Action items

Agenda Item	Action	Responsibility	Due date
1	Draft ENVRI-Hub Green Paper based on EB Strategy Meeting Minutes available for joint elaboration	Project Management	31 May 2020

Agenda Item	Action	Responsibility	Due date
2	Launch of Task Force 6	Andreas Petzold	31 May 2020
3	Definition of TF6 Use Cases	TF6/ Andreas Petzold	30 June 2020

4.7 6th EB meeting, 25 August 2020, virtual

Meeting minutes

1. Welcome and approval of agenda Andreas Petzold

Agenda was approved.

2. Update by the project office Katrin Seemeyer / Andreas Petzold

See presentation <https://iagos-comm.iek.fz-juelich.de/dmsf/files/5313/view>

3. Updates of WP2-11

a. WP2 Magdalena Brus

Activities following the periodic report 1:

1. Development of a digital brochure providing an overview of results developed in ENVRI-FAIR during the 1st reporting period.
2. Promotion of the specific results (website articles, social media, newsletter).
3. Development of the ENVRI-FAIR Newsletter focusing on the main results during the reporting period.

The usual day to day communications of the ENVRI-FAIR project and ENVRI community related issues (website, social media, articles, etc.) are ongoing. BEERI was supported with an internal communications tool for BEERI-related issues.

There was some work done on the ENVRI wiki, including the migration of key ENVRIplus deliverables to the new wiki platform which is just being finalized (organizing the content with tags and categories, migrating the content).

The communications strategy for the ENVRI community is being updated.

Three hands-on online workshops (September 29 - October 1, 2019) with RI communications managers were organized.

The strategy and related work plan for Deliverable 2.2 “ENVRI community building, engagement and communications strategy” is being developed.

The strategy of joint communications actions promoting the ENVRI community and its RIs is being implemented.

It was suggested and appreciated to invite Magdalena to the biweekly project management meetings on Thursdays.

b. WP3 Anca Hienola

The next BEERi meeting was prepared which will take place in November 2020. The agenda for the national and international stakeholders and industry workshops to be held in the last trimester of 2020 is completed and the invitation letter will be sent soon. Several virtual meetings have been held to finalize the agenda. Already now, many invited participants declined. So there have to be some additional efforts to provide very good reasons for joining the workshops. Magdalena volunteered to assist.

It was also suggested by Jacco Konijn to discuss in WP how to develop a relationship to GEO.

c. WP4 Helen Glaves / Ari Asmi

As regards WP4 we have recently completed and submitted deliverable D4.2 and the Policy Landscape will continuously be updated. A further meeting of the Policy Working Group will be organised for late September 2020 where the Policy framework based on the Policy Landscape will be reviewed. Results from WP5 will also be implemented.

It was suggested (Maggie) to collaborate with WP6 as the training for policies is scheduled for next year. In addition it was stressed (Andreas) that the Policy Landscape is important for the midterm review meeting.

One issue that came up is that not all beneficiaries for this work package have submitted a report to be included in the periodic report. Despite several reminders we received nothing from ICOS so it has been assumed no justification for use of resources is needed for WP4.

d. WP5 Alex Vermeulen

“Playtime is over!”

It has to be shown that the FAIRness of ENVRI has improved. In particular, more integration is needed across the subdomains which. A joint workshop of task forces scheduled for November will tackle this topic. In this workshop all TFs will be present and also the catalogue of services in EOSC will be discussed.

It was stressed (Angeliki) that the information flow from the TFs to the subdomains is important.

e. WP6 Maggie Hellström

See presentation <https://iagos-comm.iek.fz-juelich.de/dmsf/files/5316/view>

WP6 and WP4 need to start a close collaboration on training on policies.

Andreas: In addition to Maria Johannsson (ICOS). Barbara Magagna (EAA) has also applied as FAIR champion.

f. WP7 Zhiming Zhao

Weekly meetings were organized during summer to update the status of partners.

D7.1 (TIB and other partners) was finished. It has been internally reviewed, and will be ready for submission shortly.

The ENVRI Knowledge base and D7.3 (UvA and other partners) are being worked on. Bi-weekly meetings were organized during summer. The deliverable structure has been agreed. It will include: requirements, technology review, architecture, current status and software demonstrator.

For the EOSC Earlier Adopter program (UvA and other partners) one intermedia report meeting was organized by EOSC. The EAP projects will have 3 more months after this year. (Wiki, and PPT in the last meeting)

Training on Knowledge base (KB) (TIB/EAA) was delivered, and one on Cloud computing (UvA). The EOSC provides testbed for lab assignment.

Concerning the support of the subdomains the focus is on the gap analyses and on the implementation plans.

Next steps:

Finalize D7.3 (T7.2), (software demo)

Content of the ENVRI KB (FAIRness, Service portfolio and demonstrator), has been presented in June; User environment (Search, Graphical navigation, Triple stores)

Earlier adopter program (in T7.3)

Individual contact to each subdomain: present what we have and collect cases

New FAIRness demonstrator (for T7.1)

g. WP8 Cathrine Lund Myhre

ENVRI-FAIR WP8 organizes and conducts the implementation of FAIRness in the atmospheric subdomain. WP8 is progressing well, and the work in all tasks is on schedule. WP8 has completed 3 deliverables on time, and 11 milestones were achieved. The last milestone on monitoring the implementation of FAIRness on RI level was submitted in June. Within WP8 there was a two days' virtual WS on 16-17 June 2019 mainly focusing on WP status, discussion of implementation of FAIRness and plans for the next months. All RIs were represented together with the coordinator, WP5 and WP7 colleagues; 31 participants in total. Agenda, minutes and presentations are available in Redmine (https://iagos-comm.iek.fz-juelich.de/projects/wp-08-atmosphere-subdomain-implementation/dmsf?folder_id=556), including plans for the next months.

h. WP9 Thierry Carval

Summer 2020 was the reporting season:

- WP9 participants' contributions to 1st period reports were delivered by end of June 2020.
- WP9 1st period report was delivered in time by mid-July 2020.
- 5 milestones delivered by end of June 2020.
- 1 milestone not yet delivered (M56 delayed, should be delivered soon probably this week)
- WP9 contributions to WP4, WP5 and WP7 1st period reports

The developments described in D9.3 “Marine subdomain technical specification” are underway.

The WP9 general meeting is scheduled on 8-9 September 2020.

This meeting will focus on D9.4 “Marine subdomain implementation” of FAIR services (as described and planned in D9.3).

Half a day will be reserved for D9.8 “Marine subdomain interoperability use case” technical specifications.

i. WP10 Keith Jeffery

Essentially the EPOS catalog is already FAIR but is being further improved. A mapping from EPOS catalog to EOSC service catalog has been done. EMSO and NOC are improving their catalogs. WP10 people are involved in WP TFs, leading TF1 and TF2. It was stressed, that we need to agree to the ENVRI-Hub architecture quickly.

WP10 needs very soon clear policies (WP4) to define the architectural elements for AAAI relating solid earth domain to ENVRI-Hub and EOSC .

WP10 needs very soon to have an agreed architecture for ENVRI-FAIR so that (with WP7) WP10 can start implementing that which is required to interoperate solid earth subdomain RIs with the ENVRIHub and EOSC.

It was stated that these requirements are true for all subdomain workpackages. See also presentation <https://iagos-comm.iek.fz-juelich.de/dmsf/files/5308/view>

j. WP11 Dario Papale / Alberto Basset

WP11 worked mainly on the milestones and report in these last months but also organized a WP11 virtual meeting for September 8th in order to coordinate the efforts around the test cases selected in the Deliverable 11.1 preparation. Activities on the test cases started and have been also implemented in the timeline that is part of the Task11.3 Milestones. The next steps will be to focus on these test cases that should help to identify better practical common developments in the sub-domain.

4. Updates of the Task Forces (TF)

a. TF1 and TF2 Keith Jeffery see presentations

<https://iagos-comm.iek.fz-juelich.de/dmsf/files/5309/view>

<https://iagos-comm.iek.fz-juelich.de/dmsf/files/5310/view>

b. TF3 Angeliki Adamaki

Next meeting will be in September. In November collaboration with WP6 in planned. There have been working groups established on the FAIR architecture and the PID service ecosystem.

c. TF4 Alex Vermeulen

The focus in TF4 is on data protection, information certification and common triple store solutions for the whole ENVRI community.

d. TF5 no participant present

The work in TF5 is ongoing, there are discussions outside ENVRI-FAIR. WP1-4 meetings include TF5 issues.

e. TF6 Andreas Petzold

See presentation <https://iagos-comm.iek.fz-juelich.de/dmsf/files/5315/view>

Conclusion: Documentation of services available at the EOSC portal and how to use them should become a task for TF6. There will be a TF workshop in November with the support from all TF leaders. During this workshop, the representation of the project to EOSC will be shaped.

5. European Green Deal Call Andreas Petzold

See presentation <https://iagos-comm.iek.fz-juelich.de/dmsf/files/5314/view>

A preparatory meeting will be organized in September after the publication of the call which is expected for 18 September. (Alex/Werner/Cathrine/Andreas).

**6. Other upcoming events, workshops, conferences etc. related to EOSC
Andreas Petzold**

- EOSC Symposium 19 -22 October, Berlin
<https://www.eoscsecretariat.eu/news-opinion/save-date-eosc-symposium-2020>
- 2nd ESFRI RIs-EOSC Workshop "Research Infrastructures shaping EOSC"
<https://www.eoscsecretariat.eu/events/2nd-esfri-ris-eosc-workshop-research-infrastructures-shaping-eosc>
- European Research and Innovation Days, 22 - 24 September, virtual event
https://ec.europa.eu/info/research-and-innovation/events/upcoming-events/european-research-and-innovation-days_en
- International FAIR Convergence Symposium, 30 Nov. – 4 Dec 2020
<https://www.go-fair.org/events/international-fair-convergence-symposium/>
- RDA 16th Plenary Meeting - Costa Rica (Virtual), 9.-12. November 2020
<https://www.rd-alliance.org/plenaries/rda-16th-plenary-meeting-costa-rica-virtual>

7. AOB Andreas Petzold

INFRAEOSC-03 proposal was submitted.

8. Decisions

1. The midterm review meeting will take place on 10/11February 2021 probably in Brussels or as a virtual meeting. EC project office has confirmed the date and agreed to a virtual meeting.

9. Action items

Agenda Item	Action	Responsibility	Due date
1.	Review WP reports in technical report	All	27-08-2020

4.8 7th EB meeting, 20 October 2020, virtual

Meeting minutes

1. Welcome and approval of agenda Andreas Petzold

Agenda was approved.
Recording approved.

2. ENVRI community policy towards EOSC Andreas Petzold

(see [slides](#)) How to handle the increasing number of requests for supporting EOSC and contributing to specific projects? A policy how to deal with these request is needed.

Current situation:

The objective of ENVRI-FAIR in this context is to develop the ENVRI-Hub and to participate in EOSC Future in WP3, WP6 and TSPs.

Various teams within subdomains of ENVRI or individual RIs have been participating in EOSC-Hub essentially as use-cases.

It was suggested to raise the issue in Redmine and apply it to group for these kind of requests which will decide.

Andreas will contact the WP leads concerned to nominate members for this EOSC interaction group.

It is important for the visibility of the project and its results to participate in / answer to these kind of events / request, because if you do not you will not be invited any more.

3. ENVRI week Katrin Seemeyer / Andreas Petzold

The ENVRI week will take place as a fully virtual meeting. In addition, the tool WONDER can be used for social social interaction, coffee breaks, having a beer in the evening etc. The office which hosted the EAC could organize the meeting, including registrations for limited meetings.

At the ENVRI week mainly results will be reported in plenary sessions. This will make the meeting shorter, there will be time to finalise the preparation for the midterm review and all sessions can be attended as there are only plenary sessions.

A training event in cooperation with WP7 is planned and will take about 4 hours. But also a general report on the training activities should be included in the agenda. A short technical workshop with WP7 should also be included, ca. 2 h.

The agenda of the ENVRI week will be revised accordingly.

4. Midterm Review Katrin Seemeyer / Andreas Petzold

After some discussion the suggestion to change the agenda to

Day 1: WP1-4,+12, WP5+TFs and Impact and Day 2: WP7, WP8-11 was accepted.

The agenda will be revised accordingly and times for each topic applied. Templates will be generated and a list of topics to cover. It was also suggested to record the presentations in advance. For this work a space in NextCloud will be generated.

5. Request for extension of the project? Andreas Petzold

After the midterm review a clear overview on the status of each WP will be available and then this decision can be taken.

6. AOB Andreas Petzold

Next EB meeting Andreas Petzold

A Doodle poll for the next EB meeting in the first 2 weeks of December will be sent around.

Requests to contribute to Maggie Hellström

- FAIR metrics
<https://docs.google.com/document/d/1jcfda2eF-UL0nxTcQyNbMyJAbZCOqh9WvPy7RRtsTKk/edit?usp=sharing>
- PID Architecture for the EOSC
<https://docs.google.com/document/d/1T-bpNsmuxQewsLq48XTyUJoe0lsV7poaXohpgDo9W34/edit?usp=sharing>

7. Decisions

Create the EOSC interaction group for dealing with request concerning EOSC support.

The ENVRI week will take place as a fully virtual meeting.

Change agenda (see above)

Wait until after the midterm review to decide on the request for extension of the project.

8. Action items

Agenda Item	Action	Responsibility	Due date
2.	Contact the WP leads concerned to nominate members for EOSC interaction group	Andreas Petzold	
3.	Revised agenda for ENVRI week	Andreas Petzold, Katrin Seemeyer	
4.	Change agenda	Andreas Petzold, Katrin Seemeyer	
4.	Generate space in NextCloud	Angeliki Adamaki	
6.	Doodle poll for the next EB meeting	Katrin Seemeyer	

4.9 8th EB meeting, 8 January 2021, virtual

Meeting minutes

1. Welcome and approval of agenda Andreas Petzold

Agenda was approved.
Andreas thanked Cathrine for being the chair in 2020.

2. Election of a new chair Andreas Petzold

Helen Graves was proposed as the chair for 2021.
She was elected and accepted the election.

3. Status of project Katrin Seemeyer

A short overview on the status of the reporting of the period reports, deliverables and milestones was given (see [file](#)).

4. Status of EOSC Future Andreas Petzold / Ari Asmi

(see [file](#), slide 10 - 13) In the discussion it was noted that the development of EOSC in the related projects is very slow and the focus of ENVRI-FAIR should rather be on ENVRI-FAIR and the ENVRI-Hub. In addition, a stronger engagement of BEERi for feedback was suggested.

5. Amendment Katrin Seemeyer

(see [file](#), slide 14) The content of the third amendment was summarized.
As the Research Executive Agency (REA) might be more strict concerning sticking to timelines and other numbers it was suggested to adapt – if necessary - the due dates of the deliverables and milestones due in 2021 (see [file](#), slide 4-9).
Due to the COVID-19 pandemic almost nobody was able to travel in 2019, thus there might be travel costs which could be shifted into personnel costs.
If WP leads think that they would like to adapt due dates or shift costs send the numbers to Katrin Seemeyer (<mailto:k.seemeyer@fz-juelich.de>) until the end of January.
Please note: You do not have to change the numbers but if there are changes you can already foresee then it would look better to REA to change them now.
During the discussion it was also mentioned that it is possible to extend the project by 6 months. But the decision for this was postponed until after the ENVRI week.

6. ENVRI week Andreas Petzold

The basic details and the agenda of the ENVRI week were presented (see [file](#), slide 15-23). For social gathering at the ENVRI week the tool Wonder was proposed and a short video of that shown (see [file](#), slide 23).

The proposed solution of livestreaming to include non-GA participants in the General Assembly meeting was dismissed as the participants of the livestream cannot pose question in the chat. Thus, another technical solution will be evaluated, e.g. webinar with more co-hosts.

It was suggested to add more information on each session.

7. Midterm review Katrin Seemeyer

A preliminary timeline for the preparation of the midterm review was presented (see [file](#), slide 24).

8. AOB Andreas Petzold

It was noted that Sanna Sorvari Sundet took over a position outside FMI and had to quit the project. Her tasks in WP3 will be taken over by Paolo and Anca.

John Picard also quit the project and a replacement has to be discussed.

9. Decisions

Helen will be chair for 2021.

10. Action items

Agenda Item	Action	Responsibility	Due date
1.	Discuss replacement for John Picard in WPI-4 meeting.	Andreas Petzold	
2.			

4.10 9th EB meeting, 3 February 2021, virtual

Meeting minutes

1. Welcome and approval of agenda Andreas Petzold

Agenda was approved.

2. Reflection on ENVRI week 2021

Andreas started with some [Reflections on the ENVRI week 2021](#).

As a result of the following discussion, it came out that it has to be decided on the sustainability of e.g., the Knowledge Base and the ENVRI-Hub. It was mentioned that the ENVRI-Hub is a demonstrator – Proof of Concept – if there is sufficient uptake by the community it could be extended if the project still has resources.

It was further suggested to have more input by the RIs in the next ENVRI week.

3. Status of EOSC Future

Ari Asmi presented the current status of the EOSC Future project.

In the discussion it was mentioned that there is a risk that the expectations of the other communities might be too high, although the participants of EOSC Future are a wider ENVRI community. Still collaboration is of intrinsic interest to the ENVRI community and the runtime of the project is relatively short (2.5 years).

Interaction with EOSC should be limited to a minimum.

4. Financial status of the project

Katrin Seemeyer presented the current financial status of the project. According to that a cost-neutral extension of the project would be possible. As there were some objections to this the decision was postponed to the next EB meeting.

5. Status of Amendment III

The third amendment to the Grant Agreement was accepted and no veto was used. In addition, beneficiaries can adapt due dates of milestones and deliverables, if it is already foreseeable that they will be delayed. As a lot of travel cost could not be used due to the COVID-19 measures it would also be possible to shift travel cost to personnel costs. For these two items no amendment is necessary, but it would look better to the REA.

If any partner would like to adapt the numbers, please contact Katrin Seemeyer (k.seemeyer@fz-juelich.de).

6. Second Periodic Report

The second periodic report is due in February 2022 and preparation will start in October 2021. Deadline should not be in holiday time and the timeline will be adapted accordingly.

7. Midterm review (timeline and preparation)

The European Commission suggested to postpone the midterm review to M38 (Feb 2022) which would be right after the second period report. As the project will only run until December 2022 this is not a midterm review but a project review. As this has to be arranged with the REA timeline and conditions are still unclear, but preparations will probably start in September 2021.

8. AOB

The next EB meeting will be at the end of March. A poll will be sent out for a suitable date.

9. Decisions

The decision for the extension of the project was postponed to the next EB meeting.

10. Action items

Agenda Item	Action	Responsibility	Due date
7.	Adapt timeline for the second period report	Katrin Seemeyer	
8.	Poll for next EB meeting in March	Katrin Seemeyer	

4.11 10th EB meeting, 30 March 2021, virtual

Meeting minutes

8. Next meetings Andreas Petzold

As decided in the previous meeting EB meetings will be every 2 month on the last Tuesday of the month (([file](#), slides 34).

- 25.5.2021 13:00-15:00
- 27.7.2021 13:00-15:00
- 28.9.2021 13:00-15:00
- 30.11.2021 13:00-15:00

As the 27 July 2021 would be in the summer break it was suggested to cancel this meeting. It was decided to postpone this decision to the next meeting.

9. AOB Andreas Petzold

- The ENVRplus website has not been available for some time now. It was not transferred to STRATO. So, it was not clear what happened.
- It was decided to delete recordings of ENVRI week, except training and the policy landscape analysis.
- EGI-ACE call for use cases is now open. Katrin will forward the email to the EB members to forward them to the RIs.

10. Decisions

- ENVRI-Hub: start with the simple system as described in option 1 and step by step expand on it in the direction of option 2

11. Action items

Agenda Item	Action	Responsibility	Due date
3.	Discuss technical implementation of ENVRI-Hub	Rita Gomes, Zhiming Zhao	
5.	Nominate participants for the communications WS	All	asap
9.	Forward email about EGI-ACE call for use cases	Katrin Seemeyer	asap

4.12 11th EB meeting, 25 May 2021, virtual

Meeting minutes

1. Welcome and approval of agenda Helen Glaves

Agenda ([file](#), slide 2) was approved.

2. Extension of the project Andreas Petzold

Andreas suggested a cost-neutral extension of the whole project for 6 months corresponding to 30 June 2023 ([file](#), slide 3) as due to ongoing work and travel restrictions due to the COVID-19 pandemic the conduction of the project is delayed. As all the work packages will be extended this means that all the work package leaders need to stay fully engaged until the extended end of the project. Unused travel budget could be used for personnel cost for the extension period. This must be explained in the technical report. WP leads will have to check with all the partners in their work packages if they agree with the extensions. This proposal was supported by the participants without objections. A Redmine issue will be sent to all EB members with this information. They will have to guarantee that all the work can be done.

3. Dates for project review

Katrin Seemeyer

Katrin presented the result of the poll for dates for the project review in February/March 2022 ([file](#), slide 4). All members of the block these dates in their calendars. Katrin will send these dates to Christos Chatzimichail our new contact person at the REA (Research Executive Agency). After the meeting he has already answered that the project review will be on the 1st or 2nd of March 2022.

4. Status of the project

Katrin presented the status of the project ([file](#), slide 5-8), including deliverables, milestones, the fourth amendment and next EB meetings.

In addition, the table in Redmine (https://iagos-comm.iek.fz-juelich.de/projects/envri-fair/wiki/List_of_RIs) containing contact persons for general aspects, data centre, training and communications should be checked. Additions or corrections can be edited or sent by email to k.seemeyer@fz-juelich.de.

5. Past and upcoming events Jacco Konijn, Magdalena Brus, Ari Asmi, Katrin Seemeyer

Jacco reported on the RDA co-located event where ENVRI-Hub and the activities of the ENVRI-FAIR task forces were presented. He also reported on the ESS12 and ESS13 sessions at the EGU General Assembly where i.a., the ICOS carbon portal, EPOS-Norway, SIOS data management systems were presented and the ENVRI-Hub.

Katrin reported on the input to the FAIRsFAIR Synchronisation workshop Pillar Sessions ([file](#), slide 11) by Maggie, Maria Johnson, Barbara Magagna and Ari.

Magdalena reported on the planned contributions to the EOSC Symposium 2021 ([file](#), slide 12).

Ari reported that there will be a Science Clusters Workshop with the European Commission in June where the future work of the clusters will be discussed.

Magdalena stressed that it is important to discuss who will attend which event to attend and what will be presented there. This will be the topic of the ENVRI-FAIR Communications Workshop in June or August 2021.

6. Status ENVRI-Hub Andreas Petzold

Andreas reported on the development of the ENVRI-Hub ([file](#), slide 13-17).

7. Strategy for participation in EOSC-related HEU calls Andreas Petzold

It was decided to discuss this topic at the next BEERi meeting (to be organized in June 2021).

8. AOB Helen Glaves

- Andreas: **Reporting mechanisms for related projects**Dick: There is a call (**HORIZON-INFRA-2021-SERV-01-06**) **for developing more capabilities for research infrastructures on imaging using artificial intelligence**. EGI wants to coordinate a proposal for this call and they are looking for use cases. Dick already has an idea for the marine domain and suggested the other domain to join this proposal. The deadline is September 2021. They want to set up the framework for the proposal by June. Dick will circulate this call in the ENVRI community. People interested should contact Dick directly.

9. Decisions

- none

10. Action items

Agenda Item	Action	Responsibility	Due date
2.	Ask WP leads about the extension of the project	Andreas Petzold / Katrin Seemeyer	asap
3.	Contact Christos Chatzimichail with the preferred dates for the project review.	Katrin Seemeyer	done
4.	Check contact persons for RIs.	All	Next meeting
5.	Organise communication workshop	Magdalena Brus	Started
6.	Send slides on the ENVRI-Hub to Angeliki	Andreas Petzold	Before Monday
7.	Put the topic EOSC-related HEU call on the BEERi agenda	Ulpu Leijala	done
8.	Put the report on related projects on the next agenda	Katrin Seemeyer / Andreas Petzold	Before next meeting
9.	Contact Dick if you have use cases	All	asap

4.13 12th EB meeting, 27 July 2021, virtual

Meeting minutes

1. Welcome and approval of agenda Helen Glaves

Agenda ([file](#), slide 2) was approved.

2. Status of the project Andreas Petzold

The status of the project ([file](#), slide 3-6) reviewed the status of deliverables, milestones, the fourth amendment and next EB meetings.

MS 24 was updated since the connected workshop is now scheduled for 24 September 2021 and the milestone was set for M34 (October 2021). The same delivery date was set for MS 27. Both changes have been corrected on slide 4.

MS 88 – 92 should also be reached, like MS 88. This needs to be checked by the project management and to be updated in the portal accordingly.

D3.5 is under risk since the responsible person (John Piccard) left EMSO. The readjustment of the goals of D3.5 should be done in connection to Amendment 5. Anca and Andreas will take care of this once the input by Juanjo has been received.

3. Extension of the project

The status of the project extension request was summarized ([file](#), slide 7). Work package leaders were reminded to provide input on the requested shifts of deliverables and milestones by 9 August the latest, so that Katrin can start preparing Amendment 5 after her return from vacation.

4. Project review

The status of the project review preparation was summarized ([file](#), slides 8 - 11). The presented timeline for the presentation was accepted.

The overall structure of the event was approved but the timing was adjusted to give more time to discussions, see slide 11 and the programme on Redmine. It was suggested to limit the number of slides to be shown per time slot. Partners also request the provision of templates for work packages other than subdomains. The project management team will take care of this.

Ari suggested again the development of a storyline for the entire event. The project management team will also take care of this.

5. Past and upcoming events

Andreas reported shortly from the EOSC Symposium and Ari from the ESFRI Cluster Workshop, see slides 12 – 14. As mentioned already in the last EB meeting the tools for monitoring the participation of ENVRI partners in events need to be improved.

Review of upcoming events:

ENVRI Summer School “Services for FAIRness” <https://envri.eu/event/save-the-date-envri-community-international-school-services-for-fairness/>

Deadline for application has been extended to 25 August.

AGU 2021 Session IN009 - A Moonshot Ambition: Creating a Globally Integrated infrastructure to Find, Access, Interoperate and Reuse Earth and Environmental Science Data to address Global Challenges; see <https://agu.confex.com/agu/fm21/prelim.cgi/Session/121360>

is organised by Anca, Jacco, Lesley Wyborn, and Amber Budden. Please consider contributions.

RDA at International Data Week 2021 <https://www.rd-alliance.org/save-date-international-data-week-2021-8%E2%80%9311-november-2021-seoul-south-korea>

This time, no co-located events are foreseen. Participation by ENVRI-FAIR contributors is encouraged.

6. Status ENVRI-Hub Andreas Petzold

Andreas reported on the progress of the ENVRI-Hub ([file](#), slide 15).

7. AOB Andreas Petzold

No AOB announced. Next EB meeting is scheduled for 28 September 2021.

8. Decisions

- No decision made

9. Action items

Agenda Item	Action	Responsibility	Due date
2.	MS 88 – 92 should also be reached, like MS 88.	Andreas Petzold / Katrin Seemeyer	asap
2.	Readjustment of the goals of D3.5 should be done in connection to Amendment 5. Information from responsible partner EMSO to WP3 lead is required.	JuanJo Danobeitia Anca Hienola/ Andreas Petzold	asap
3.	Adaptation of tasks, deliverables and milestones need to be finalized for WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5 and WP6.	WP leads to inform Katrin Seemeyer	9 August 2021
4.	Provide templates for WPs 1 to 7.	Andreas Petzold	asap

4.14 13th EB meeting, 28 September 2021, virtual

Meeting minutes

1. Welcome and approval of agenda Helen Glaves

Agenda ([file](#), slide 2) was approved.

2. Status of the project

Katrin Seemeyer

It was announced that the amendment 5 was accepted and signed by the European Commission ([file](#), slide 3). With this the project is officially extended by 6 months, corresponding to 30 June 2023.

The status of the project ([file](#), slide 4 - 7) reviewed the status of deliverables and milestones. On the slides the comments from the WP leads concerning the status were included.

3. Project review

Katrin Seemeyer

The date for the project review was finally fixed by Christos Chazimichail (REA) to the 1 March 2022 and the reviewers will be Jan Hrusak, Anne Fouilloux, Natalia Beloff ([file](#), slide 8). The [agenda](#) and the [timeline for the preparation](#) are prepared and uploaded to Redmine, as well as the [templates](#) (including a [template for the subdomains](#) and a [template for WP1-7](#)). The speakers for the second part of the project review were selected ([file](#), slide 13). The real condition test run will be on Monday 15 November 2021, 9:00 – 16:00 CET.

It was agreed that the presentations will be preliminary but should already follow the agreed structure. The slides can be revised for the ENVRI week in February 2022 to consider the latest developments and benefit from the material assembled for the RP2 and the ENVRI week. In any case, the presentations need to be harmonized among the different topics to illustrate the red line of the review meeting. The purpose of the test meeting is to see the content and structure of the presentations and to make sure that all the key topics are properly addressed by all presentation.

4. Reporting RPII

Katrin Seemeyer

The adapted templates for the beneficiary reports and the WP reports have already been distributed and the instructions for those. Katrin mentioned that the template for the beneficiary has been shortened compared to RP1. Updated instructions for the financial reporting will be provided in November ([file](#), slide 15-16).

5. Past and upcoming events

Andreas Petzold

Andreas gave a brief report on the **ERIC Forum** where he presented the ENVRI cluster.

Ari reported on the policy workshop which took place on Friday last week. A summary of the feedback of the participants can be found [here](#).

In the discussion it was pointed out that the language used in this policy development domain was not straightforward even for the RIs managers and that there is still a long way to go for the RIs to fully understand what they have to do with their governing bodies to progress on these issues.

Maggie gave an interim report on the **2021 ENVRI Community International School "Services for FAIRness"** which started on Monday 27 September 2021. The programme of this can be found [here](#). The sessions will be recorded and made available on the Training Platform.

Review of upcoming events:

- **EGU**: Anca and Jacco will prepare a session on scientific networking. Maybe a townhall meeting will be organised as well. It was also suggested to have an interactive tool (ENVRI-Hub demo) at the booth. A poster at the session would be welcome too. The EGU meeting will be a hybrid meeting with on-site sessions in Vienna.
- **AGU**: This will probably be a fully online meeting.
- **EOSC Symposium** will be co-organised by EOSC Future in the end of June 2022. WP2 will organise contributions to this.

6. Status of related projects

Andreas reported that the work for **EOSC Future** is ongoing, although there are some administrative issues to overcome. The strategic board had several meetings with the Secretary General of the EOSC association to align the activities of EOSC Future with the EOSC Association and to ensure that in the EOSC A Task Forces EOSC Future is represented.

Keith presented the working groups which will be set up in WP3 of EOSC Future and his

[proposal of a WG on metadata](#) (file, slide 10-21). The members of the Executive Board are asked to forward and discuss this with the RIs in their WPs. The RIs are requested to endorse the WP and nominate members.

Ariane gave an [overview on the status of ATMO-ACCESS](#).

PAUL: Paul will start next month.

RI Urbans: Paolo reported that there are some issues here concerning data management. Paolo will report on PAUL and RI Urbans in one of the next EB meetings.

7. Status ENVRI-Hub Rita Gomes

Rita reported on the progress of the ENVRI-Hub ([file](#), slide 22-24).

8. AOB

- **GDPR Report:** GDPR is part of Task Force 5. Keith initiated a survey on GDPR in the participating RIs which is given in the [GDPR report](#). He suggested to include the GDPR activities into the WP4 policy activities. WP4 leads agreed with that.
- **Documentation of Events:** Katrin showed the current “documentation” of events in Redmine. Katrin mentioned that it is difficult to get the information on contributions of ENVRI-FAIR to events. She can only document information given to her.

9. Decisions

- No decision made

10. Action items

No action items.

4.15 14th EB meeting, 30 November 2021, virtual

Meeting minutes

1. Welcome and approval of agenda Ari Asmi

Agenda ([file](#), slide 2) was approved.

2. New WP7 co-lead Katrin Seemeyer

As Dick Schaap – currently co-lead of WP7 – is very busy it was agreed to add Peter Thijsse as co-lead for WP7 ([file](#), slide 3). It was not yet clear if he will be an additional co-lead or substitute Dick. Katrin will clarify this by email.

3. Updates on ENVRI Week 2022, based on current COVID situation Katrin Seemeyer / Ari Asmi

It was agreed to do the ENVRI week as a fully virtual event. In this case it was suggested to work on the agenda to have shorter meetings and not for the whole day. In addition, the organisers of planned workshops and trainings agreed to shift those before the ENVRI week.

It was mentioned that very few people registered for the event yet. If you have not yet registered please register here

<https://envri.eu/envri-week-2022-registration/>

4. Discussion of project review test run Ari Asmi

The available information on the reviewers were presented ([file](#), slide 7-9). Jan Hrusak will probably be interested in the organisational details and the infrastructures, whereas Anne Fouilloux has a technical

and user-oriented focus and Natalia Beloff has also a technical focus and might also be interested in the QA/QC aspects.

It was suggested to work on the alignment of the presentations and to prepare for the (technical) questions. The sustainability should be stressed and addressed in all/more than one presentation.

The current agenda can be found here

https://iagos-comm.fz-juelich.de/projects/project-meetings/wiki/Project_review

A summary of the feedback given to the presentations at the test run can be found here

<https://fileshare.icos-cp.eu/apps/onlyoffice/s/B8e2HegfP4ZXaws?fileId=2210810>

In this file also the general guidance for all presentation is summarised. Feel free to add your own feedback and use the file to optimise your presentation.

If there are any questions on the project review don't hesitate to contact Andreas, Ari or Katrin.

5. Project brief Ari Asmi

The European Commission requested a project brief on implementation of Open Science and EOSC targets. They asked for statements on 5 topics which are given in a shared document available here <https://fileshare.icos-cp.eu/apps/onlyoffice/s/B8e2HegfP4ZXaws?fileId=2184435>.

In the document the topics are given and the key words which were provided by the EC. It was asked for a concise report with about 1 page per topic.

For some of the topics already some input has been given (Thank you to the authors!).

Please, review the input available and add your own input.

As the content of the project brief – at least the last topic on cluster collaboration – will be aligned with the other clusters please do the editing until the end of this week, i.e., **by Friday 3 December 2021**. The final text must be submitted to the EC by 10 December 2021.

Katrin will send out a reminder for input to the project brief.

6. AOB

The next meeting will be on 25 January 2022, 13:00 – 15:00 CET.

The participants were reminded that the WP reports are due on **15 December 2021** (see also the timeline for the reporting <https://iagos-comm.fz-juelich.de/attachments/1172>).

Jacco and Barbara mentioned the training for I-ADOPT which will take place in January/February 2022.

Event 1 will be held on Friday January 21, 9.00h - 12.30h CET, through Zoom

Event 2 will be held on Thursday February 17, 9.00h - 12.30h CET, through Zoom

More details on the events can be found here

https://docs.google.com/document/d/1o3snhCdx6Nys_STLbu_epKRieruH7xe5rlAVfYP4Af8/edit

Anca and Jacco are organising a session at the EGU meeting 2022. The session can be found here

<https://meetingorganizer.copernicus.org/EGU22/session/42424>

7. Decisions

- Peter Thijsee was accepted as a co-lead for WP7.
- ENVRI week fully virtual meeting.

8. Action items

Agenda Item	Action	Responsibility	Due date
2.	Ask for clarification whether Peter will be additional co-lead or substitute Dick	Katrin	done
5.	Send out reminder to provide input to the project brief	Katrin	asap
5.	Provide input to the project brief	all	3 Dec 2021

4.16 15th EB meeting, 25 January 2022, virtual

Meeting minutes

1. Welcome and approval of agenda Anca Hienola

Agenda ([file](#), slide 2) was approved.

2. Election of a new chair Andreas Petzold

As there were already chairs from the marine subdomain (2019) the atmosphere subdomain (2020) and the solid earth subdomain (2021) this year the biodiversity / ecosystems subdomain will chair the EB meetings ([file](#), slide 3). Alberto Basset was suggested by the PO office. He was elected and accepted the election.

3. Changes in Executive Board Katrin Seemeyer

The changes in the Executive Board were presented ([file](#), slide 4).

4. Status of the project Katrin Seemeyer

A short overview on the status of the project was given including the timeline for the reporting and the project reviews ([file](#), slide 4), a summary of the number of deliverables submitted in RPI and RPII and a list of deliverables due in the first half of 2022 ([file](#), slide 6) as well as a summary of the number of milestones reached so far and a list of milestones due in the first half of 2022 ([file](#), slide 7-8). Here it was pointed out the responsible partner for D5.5 is not ICOS but INGV (this now corrected in the slides). Concerning the second periodic report ([file](#), slide 8), RPII covers M19 to M36 corresponding to Juli 2020 to December 2021. For the technical report almost all work package reports were delivered and included, a few questions will be sent out to the WP (co-)leads later. A few financial statements have already been entered in the EU participants portal. The deadline for submitting the financial statements to the coordinator is **31 January 2022**. It is not necessary to send the financial report to the PO before submission to the coordinator. But if you want the report to be checked before submission you can send it to Claudia de Laat (c.de.laat@fz-juelich.de)

5. Project review Andreas Petzold

A short reminder on the major aspects to consider for the presentations at the project review was given ([file](#), slide 10-11). Some of the feedback given at the first test run can be found here <https://fileshare.icos-cp.eu/apps/onlyoffice/s/B8e2HegfP4ZXaws?fileId=2210810> and the agenda for the project review can be found here https://iagos-comm.iek.fz-juelich.de/projects/project-meetings/wiki/Project_review) The presentation given at the first test run can be found here https://iagos-comm.iek.fz-juelich.de/projects/project-meetings/dmsf?folder_id=926. For the second test run at the ENVRI week the presentation should be in a final state – last minute adjustments are possible - and should be uploaded to this folder https://iagos-comm.iek.fz-juelich.de/projects/project-meetings/dmsf?folder_id=927. It was pointed out that the reviewers are mainly – two out of three – technical people and the presentations at the project review should demonstrate the technical progress and especially the interoperability. More information on the reviewers can be found here <https://iagos-comm.iek.fz-juelich.de/dmsf/files/6509/view>. At the second test run we will mainly go through the slides to check if they are fit for purpose.

6. EOSC Andreas Petzold, Keith Jeffery

Keith presented on ENVRI and EOSC, ENVRI-FAIR and EOSC-Future, different ways to handle metadata and User Requests ([file](#), slide 12-34), including a short overview on OpenAIRE. Pros and cons of some of the solutions were discussed and suggested to work on a presentation for non-technical people to take that to the BEERi meeting. In addition, there should be further discussion at TF1, at the technical workshop during the ENVRI week and the WP5 meeting at the ENVRI week.

Andreas reported on the Strategic Oversight Board of EOSC Future ([file](#), slide 36-37) and the participation of RIs involved in ENVRI-FAIR and also involved in EOSC Future ([file](#), slide 38-40). It was suggested to establish a stronger connection between the technical experts in ENVRI-FAIR and in EOSC Future. This should be discussed at the next EB meeting at the ENVRI week.

7. ENVRI-Hub

Andreas Petzold, Daniele Bailo

Andreas reported on the status of the ENVRI-Hub ([file](#), slide 47-53).

Daniele reported on the work of TF2 (AAAI) ([file](#), slide 54-59) and TF2 (Catalog of Services) ([file](#), slide 60-66). A demo of the Catalog of Services can be found here <https://ics-c.epos-ip.org/demo/k8s-epos-deploy/envri-fair-catalogue/api/webapi/v1.3/swagger-ui/>.

8. Decisions

Alberto Basset will be the new chair of the Executive Board 2022.

9. Action items

Agenda Item	Action	Responsibility	Due date
4.	Send out a reminder for the financial statement	Katrin / Claudia de Laat	asap
7.	When will there be an internal test version of the ENVRI-Hub be available? discuss	Andreas / Katrin / Rita	This week

4.17 16th EB meeting, 2 February 2022, virtual at the ENVRI week 2022

Meeting minutes

1. Project review

Andreas Petzold

The timeline for the preparation of the project review was agreed.

The project officer from the REA – Christos Chatzimichail – wants us to provide the presentation for the project review by Friday, **25 February 2022**. The finalised presentation will be uploaded to Redmine until **21 February 2022** here

https://iagos-comm.iwk.fz-juelich.de/projects/project-meetings/dmsf?folder_id=939.

As the FAIR convergence workshop will take place on 22 February 2022 and the data from this workshop are needed for Barbara's presentation, she can upload her slides until **23 February 2022**.

At the test run in the chat a discussion whether SeaDataNET was a Research Infrastructure came up. It was clarified that according to the rules of participation could not participate as a Research Infrastructure, as they are not at the ESFRI list. So we have 13 Research Infrastructures in the project and 2 technical partners, SeaDataNET and the University of Amsterdam (UiA).

It was suggested to prepare an outline for all presentations.

It was suggested work with the feedback list generated in the test run.

<https://fileshare.icos-cp.eu/apps/onlyoffice/s/B8e2HegfP4ZXaws?fileId=2280465> and don't do another test run but rather work in smaller groups to harmonise and finalise the presentations. Here it would be very important to make sure that the **time** for the presentations **is kept**. If there are any further questions, ask Andreas for support.

Common icons are not yet available, but Katri will check with the designer what was/will be done.

The KPIs will not be included in the Communications presentation but by Andreas in the Impact presentation were all KPI will be included.

Concerning the sustainability this should be brought up in BEERi.

4.18 17th EB meeting, 29 March 2022, virtual

Meeting minutes

1. Project review Andreas Petzold

Changes in the technical report

Andreas presented his changes in the technical report as requested from the reviewers.

After the discussion it was agreed that Keith, Barbara and Maggie were asked to send their additions/changes to Andreas by tomorrow.

Recommendations for future work

Concerning the recommendations for future work the participants agreed that ENVRI-FAIR should respond to that and clarify our point of view. As the deadline for submission of “observations” is very short – 15 April 2022 - a shared document will be set up and all participants can add the comments. (Already done see here https://fileshare.icos-cp.eu/apps/onlyoffice/s/B8e2HegfP4ZX_aws?fileId=2331092).

2. Redistribution of budget Katrin Seemeyer

All partners were asked to check their remaining budget and consider if they will be able to claim all of it in the next reporting period. Until now we received very few answers on that and only one beneficiary responded that part of this can be redistributed.

3. AOB Andreas Petzold

No AOB.

4. Decisions

- Submit “observations” concerning the recommendations for future work.

5. Action items

Agenda Item	Action	Responsibility	Due date
2.	Send your additions/comments to the technical report to Andreas	Keith, Barbara, Maggie	done
2.	Set up a shared document for response on the recommendations	Katrin	Done
2.	Add your comments to the shared document (see above)	All	asap
3.	Check your budget and answer Katrin’s email	All	asap

4.19 18th EB meeting, 31 May 2022, virtual

Meeting minutes

1. Welcome and approval of agenda Alberto Basset

Agenda ([file](#), slide 2) was approved.

2. Status of the project (deliverables, milestones, amendment 7) Katrin Seemeyer

Katrin gave an overview on the status of the project including deliverables, milestones and amendment 7 ([file](#), slide 3-7). Cathrine added that MS33 and MS43 are shifted to M45. This is an item in amendment 7 but not implemented in the GA yet.

3. Project review Report: Answer to observations Katrin Seemeyer

We received the final letter for the project review report stating “*Having received your observations (Ref. Ares(2022)3035253 - 14/04/2022), we fully maintain our reasoning as explained in the draft review report letter.*” As that gave rise to some concerns within the consortium the German National Contact Point was contacted and their statement was: These are just recommendations, meaning that they are not legally binding and they are not joint with a non-payment of funding ([file](#), slide 8).

4. Redistribution of budget Katrin Seemeyer

A few partners offered a limited amount of their budget to be redistributed within the consortium, 48,000€. It was suggested to postpone the decision how do redistribute the funding until next year when the use of funding is more clear.

5. Topics from WP3 Valentina Tegas/ Paolo Laj

Milestone MS10 - Workshop with e-infrastructures and other EOSC actors

The discussion concerning the workshop was postponed as Anca could not attend the meeting.

Service catalogue for industry

Valentina Tegas

Valentina Tegas (WP3) gave an overview on the deliverable D3.5 - Catalogue of services targeted for the private sector (deliverable: <https://iagos-comm.iek.fz-juelich.de/dmsf/files/6869/view>, slides: <https://iagos-comm.iek.fz-juelich.de/dmsf/files/6901/view>) and the further proceedings with the results were discussed. It is not yet clear how the results can be published and where (ENVRI-Hub or ENVRI Website). It was also suggested to ask – at least selected people from the private sector – what they would like to use and what they expect. But WP3 argued that this should be done by the RIs themselves. It was specified that “private sector” here means non-academic sector.

In the discussion it was stressed that it needs to be defined more clearly what we call a service. This has already been discussed in TF1 and is considered a very wide field. A meeting between WP3 and WP5 to discuss the issues involved in publication of the catalogue was suggested.

6. Report on cluster meetings

This item was skipped as Andreas Petzold could not attend the meeting.

7. Past and upcoming events

Upcoming Meetings

European Ecological Federation (EEF) Congress: LifeWatch is planning to participate (for more information see here <https://www.europeanecology.org/sfe2-gfo-eef-joint-meeting-metz-2022/>).

Past Meetings

EGU

Angeliki Adamaki

At the EGU General Assembly WP2 organized an ENVRI Booth. At the booth lunch talks were given and including a presentation of the ENVRI-Hub and a life demonstration. The booth had a good audience of about 300 visitors.

8. Status related projects

EOSC Future

Keith Jeffery

In WP3 – Architecture the expertise gathered in ENVRI concerning AAI and catalogue. Discussion on the metadata format to be used is ongoing. Concerning AAI a test with 4 RIs is planned to provide federated access to the EOSC.

ATMO-ACCESS

Paolo Laj

In this project the second call for TNS was opened. For the first call more than 70 proposals were received and the same amount is expected this time. This second call is targeting Green Deal issues. They are currently working on solutions how to provide sustainable access and define the roles of the EC and the national stakeholders. All participants are encouraged to apply for access (more information can be found here <https://www.atmo-access.eu/access-to-services/>).

PAUL

Alex Vermeulen

Preparations for the measurements in the city are ongoing. Another instance of the ICOS Carbon portal might be implemented for the data of this project. A survey on the policy makers involved is prepared.

9. Status ENVRI-Hub

This item was skipped as Andreas was present, Katrin just reported that there are no new developments, yet.

10. AOB: ENVRI Summer School

Maggie Hellström

Maggie reported on the ENVRI Summer School 2022.

General info: <https://www.lifewatch.eu/envri-community-international-summer-school-2022/School>
 registration: <https://www.lifewatch.eu/envri-community-international-summer-school-2022/registration-form/>

Deadline: June 17

Main target groups: IT architects, Research Infrastructure (RI) service developers and user support staff, and RI staff working on user interaction and community/network building

IMPORTANT: Currently underrepresented subdomains: Atmosphere, Marine & Solid Earth <<-- we need your help to attract participants!

She also mentioned 2 open Webinars:

These are open to everyone interested, in and out of the ENVRI Community!

Webinar #1: Service validation & evaluation: making sure your services are up to the task - Friday 17 June, 10:00-11:30 CEST

Webinar #2: Service documentation & tutorials: rolling out the red carpet for end users - Thursday 23 June, 10:00-11:30 CEST

Common registration form: <https://www.lifewatch.eu/envri-community-international-summer-school-2022/webinars/>

Main target groups: IT architects, Research Infrastructure (RI) service developers and user support staff, and RI staff working on user interaction and community/network building

11. Action items

Agenda Item	Action	Responsibility	Due date
5.	Organise a meeting between WP3 and WP5 to discuss catalogue issues	Valentina, Angeliki	

4.20 19th EB meeting, 27 July 2022, virtual

Meeting minutes

Due to the summer break in this meeting there were very few participants. Thus, there was just a very short general discussion.

4.21 20th EB meeting, 27 September 2022, virtual

Meeting minutes

1. Welcome and approval of agenda Alberto Basset

Agenda ([file](#), slide 2) was approved.

2. Status of the project (deliverables, milestones, amendment 7) Katrin Seemeyer

Katrin gave an overview on the status of the project including deliverables, milestones and amendment 7 and 8 ([file](#), slide 3-9).

As only about 50% of the deliverable (38 of 80) have been submitted ([file](#), slide 5) and a large number of deliverable are due by the end of the project or shortly before it was stressed that careful planning of the timelines for the preparation and review of the deliverables is necessary.

Amendment 7 was approved by the European Commission and the new documents are available in Redmine https://iagos-comm.iek.fz-juelich.de/projects/general-documents/dmsf?folder_id=977. There are already a few request for the next amendment and if there are additional request contact Katrin until 31 October 2022.

For the final project review September 2023 was suggested. However, in the discussion afterwards it was suggested to clarify with Christos Chatzimichail (REA) if the costs for travelling and hours spent on the preparation could still be claimed. In addition, September is still in the summer break for some participants, and they will not be able to attend. It was also suggested to rather have an online meeting, because during the pandemic the virtual format has been established and for environmental reason not travelling would be preferred.

3. ENVRI-FAIR final event Andreas Petzold

Andreas was invited to a few final events of other cluster projects ([file](#), slide 10) and it was discussed if ENVRI-FAIR should also organise a final event which would give ENVRI-FAIR more visibility.

It was noted that the experience with previous final events was disappointing as there was only minimum attendance from outside the project. It was suggested to rather organise smaller strategic meetings dedicated to different target communities. It is important to have a clear what we want to achieve with this meeting, which audience we want to reach and a clear message.

It was suggested to concentrate together with the other clusters on lessons learned and how to go on with the EOSC.

Jacco, Anca Hienola, and Angeliki and are working on a proposal for a session at the EGU General Assembly 2023 in April which will be an opportunity to demonstrate what has been done in the ENVRI-Hub. All participants from ENVRI-FAIR will be encouraged to send in abstracts for this session. WP6 is planning hackathon with a end user perspective which takes a lot of time and careful planning.

4. Redistribution of budget Katrin Seemeyer

A few partners offered a limited amount of their budget to be redistributed within the consortium, 48,000€ (INGV and GeoEcoMar). In addition, as Ari left the University of Helsinki (UH) UH might provide part of their budget to the ENVRI-FAIR consortium. Ari suggested 190k€ but this has still to be confirmed ([file](#), slide 11). All work package and task force leaders are asked to discuss within their WP if partner need additional funding and contact the project management until 31 October 2022.

5. Upcoming events Katrin Seemeyer

ENVRI week 2023

The ENVRI week 2023 ([file](#), slide 13) will take place in Leipzig, Germany, from 30 January 2023 to 3 February 2023 as a Face-2-Face meeting. A preliminary agenda can be found in Redmine https://iagos-comm.iek.fz-juelich.de/projects/project-meetings/wiki/ENVRI_week_2023

All WP(co-)leads are asked to consider if their need additional sessions and contact Katrin with a title and the time needed.

It was suggested to add a session on the future/sustainability of the ENVRI community, but this would rather be discussed at the BEERi meeting as here a firm commitment of the RIs is needed. This topic could also be taken up at the ENVRI community meeting.

TF6 Workshop Amsterdam

From 10 October to 11 October 2022 a TF6 workshop will be held in Amsterdam, more information can be found in Redmine https://iagos-comm.iek.fz-juelich.de/projects/task-forces/wiki/TF6_Workshop_-_October_2022.

FIP Workshops

For the FAIRness assessment 2023 by preparing the FIPs 2022 three consultation workshops ([file](#), slide 14) were organised. They will take place in the first quarter of 2023. More information on the workshops can be found in Redmine

https://iagos-comm.iek.fz-juelich.de/projects/wp-5-common-requirements-and-testbed-for-meta-data-services-community-standards-and-cataloguing/wiki/Fairness_Assessment_2022

Each participating RI is supposed to prepare their FIP 2022 until 27 March 2023.

EOSC Symposium

The EOSC Symposium ([file](#), slide 15) will be held from 14 to 17 November, in Prague and online. The cluster coordinators were asked by the European Commission to organise a session on interdisciplinary alignment and collaboration. WP3 will organize a session with e-infras and EOSC Association representatives to discuss for example possible future collaboration in the framework of the new EC calls/long term collaboration, /sustainability/ EOSC-hub.

This time no talks from ENVRI-FAIR are scheduled.

On 26 October 2022 at the **Hotzone week on FAIR** in Leiden, The Netherlands, there will be a session called “Convergence in ENVRI-FAIR using FIPs” organized by Barbara Magagna where at a panel discussion participants of ENVRI-FAIR and others will reflect from different viewpoints on the use of the FIPs.

The **RDA Plenary 20** will be held on 21–23 March 2023 in **Gothenburg** and if there is interest in a collocated event. Deadline for proposals 31 October 2022.

6. Horizon Europe calls

Andreas Petzold

HORIZON-INFRA-2023-EOSC-01-01 ([file](#), slide 16-18) which includes cascading grants. This is a call to the science clusters and Andreas will join the management team of the proposal and asks for additional organisations to join this. EPOS might be willing to join, Keith will discuss this in the managing board, also LifeWatch is interested.

HORIZON-INFRA-2023-EOSC-01-03 ([file](#), slide 19-20) the proposal is led by OpenAIRE and Andreas will join. ENVRI-FAIR is already working with OpenAIRE on a mechanism to put out metadata through OpenAIRE to the EOSC. But some more discussion would be necessary to find out what they are planning. Keith will approach Paolo on that. Afterwards this will be discussed in a smaller group.

HORIZON-INFRA-2024-EOSC-01-01 ([file](#), slide 21) this could be a follow-up to ENVRI-FAIR but it will only start in 2024. So there will be 1 year gap after the end of ENVRI-FAIR. It was suggested to discuss that at the next BEERi meeting in December 2022. But there are also other calls which might bridge the gap.

At the TF6 workshop there will be also a session on the sustainability and Andreas will present the call and other opportunities there. Andreas will summarise the outcome for the BEERi meeting.

7. AOB: Mari Best

Andreas Petzold, Mairi Best

Andreas introduced Mairi Best who will take over part of the work from Ari in WP4. Mairi Best is known in the ENVRI community as she already worked for ENVRIplus. Mairi also talked about her background and experiences.

8. Action items

Agenda Item	Action	Responsibility	Due date
2.	Clarify with Christos Chatzimichail (REA) if the costs for this could still be claimed	Katrin Seemeyer	
6.	Speak to Lili Freda about HORIZON-INFRA-2023-EOSC-01-01	Keith Jeffery	
6.	Speak to Christos about HORIZON-INFRA-2023-EOSC-01-01	Alberto Basset	
6.	Keith will approach Paolo HORIZON-INFRA-2023-EOSC-01-03	Keith Jeffery	

4.22 21st EB meeting, 29 November 2022, virtual

Meeting minutes

1. Welcome and approval of agenda Alberto Basset

Agenda ([file](#), slide 2) was approved.

2. Status of the project (deliverables, milestones, amendment 8) Katrin Seemeyer

Katrin gave an overview on the status of the project including deliverables, milestones and amendment 8 ([file](#), slide 3-10).

The date for the final project review will be on 25 or 28 September 2023. This will finally be decided by Christos Chatzimail (REA) slides ([file](#), 6). Please block both dates for the review.

The status of deliverables and milestones was not discussed in detail, it was only mentioned that as can be seen from the slides ([file](#), 7-9) some of the deliverables and milestones are already delayed. WP leads were asked to contact Katrin concerning the status or a new due date (for new due date send them before 16 December 2022).

The approval period of amendment 8 is running until 1 December 2022. After that the veto period starts, which will run until 16 December 2022. After that the amendment will be entered in the EU portal and submitted.

3. ENVRI week Katrin Seemeyer, Andreas Petzold

Katrin presented the agenda of the ENVRI week 2023 ([file](#), 11-13). Keith and Maggie confirmed that it was OK that the policy workshop and the panel discussion on PID issues run in parallel.

In the ENVRI - EOSC Future and overview on the EOSC Future project will be given by the participants in of EOSC Future.

In the open ENVRI Community meeting the future of the ENVRI Community will be discussed.

Concerning booking of rooms in the hotel, the reserved contingent of 100 hotel rooms in the hotel hosting the ENVRI week (Pentahotel Leipzig) for a fixed price of 129€ per night including breakfast will be available until 19 December 2022. Rooms can be booked via this link

<https://reservations.pentahotels.com/108162?groupID=3643576#/guestsandrooms>

or contact the hotel directly by mail and refer to “ENVRI” to make sure you get a room out of the reserved contingent for the agreed price. You should use the way with the email if you would like to arrive already on Sunday.

In the chat it was asked whether there will be a poster session. During the reception on 30 January 2023, 18:00 – 20:00 CET at the hotel posters can be presented, more information is given here

https://iagos-comm.iek.fz-juelich.de/projects/project-meetings/wiki/Reception_2023

As given there please indicate in the registration that you want to show a poster or contact Ines (i.Thelen@fz-juelich.de).

4. ENVRI-FAIR final event Andreas Petzold

Andreas presented what PaNOSC has planned for their final event ([file](#), 14-15) and suggested to do something similar. Although, some participants were still sceptic if it would be worth the effort, it was agreed that presentation of results is necessary.

It was suggested to make it an event for the wider ENVRI community.

5. ENVRI-Hub Ulrich Bundke

Uli presented the current status of the ENVRI-Hub in a live-demo. He also pointed out the actions which still have to be done by TF1 and the RIs ([file](#), 17-18) and the issues with the SHAPeNESS tool ([file](#), 19-20).

TF1 will organizing telcos with the metadata curators of each RI (Damien for WP8, Thierry and Peter for WP9, Xeni and Katrina for WP11), to complete the EPOS-DCAT-AP turtle files and ingest everything into the catalogue.

6. Horizon Europe calls Andreas Petzold, Katrin Seemeyer, Keith Jeffery

Participants of ENVRI-FAIR also work on the following EU calls

INFRA-EOSC-2023-01-01 (OSCARS proposal): Katrin, Anca, Andreas

INFRA-EOSC-2023-01-03 (coordinated by OpenAIRE): Keith

HORIZON-INFRA-2023-SERV-01-01 (coordinated by Natural Resources Institute, FI)

INFRA-EOSC-2023-01-02 (follow-up to EOSC Synergy)

Katrin gave an overview what was discussed at the last meeting for the OSCARS proposal ([file](#), 22-26).

Keith summarized the status of the proposal against the HORIZON-INFRA-2023-EOSC-01-03 call led by OpenAIRE ([file](#), 27-30).

7. AOB Andreas Petzold

The next EB meeting will take place as a face-2-face meeting on 31 January 2023 at the ENVRI week.

8. Action items

Agenda Item	Action	Responsibility	Due date
3.	Clarify deadline for booking and booking for early arrival	Katrin Seemeyer	
4.	Arrange a meeting with Katri, Jacco and Andreas concerning the final event	Andreas Petzold	

4.23 22nd EB meeting, 31 January 2023, Leipzig, DE at the ENVRI week 2023

Meeting minutes

0. Approval of the EB chair 2023 - proposed Anca Hienola

The proposed chair for the Executive Board in 2023 – Anca Hienola – was unanimously accepted.

1. Welcome and approval of agenda Anca Hienola

Agenda ([file](#), slide 3) was approved.

2. Status of the project (deliverables, milestones, amendment 8) Katrin Seemeyer

Katrin gave an overview on the status of the project ([file](#), slide 4-12), including the final project review, which was cancelled by the REA, the timeline and procedure for the final periodic report, deliverable and milestones and amendment 8.

3. ENVRI-FAIR final event

The idea was to have a final event in Brussels in June, back-to-back with an ICOS event. This still has to be decided ([file](#), slide 13).

4. Participation in Horizon Europe Calls / Sustainability of products beyond ENVRI-FAIR

([file](#), slide 14) **Memorandum of Understanding (MoU)**: The ENVRI Community started an effort to establish a Memorandum of Understanding as formal framework for the active and united ENVRI Community, but formal agreement by all RIs could not be achieved. In the European Research Area and in the current and future European Research Framework Programmes, the science clusters of ESFRI research infrastructures, have gained a leading role in the strategic planning of the infrastructure support and development programmes on the European level. Each science cluster needs to create a sustainable governance structure that is independent of time-limited research projects. Some of the science clusters have already established cooperation agreements, the others are close to finalisation. Action item of the BEERi Sustainability Working Group, meeting on Thursday and Friday.

In addition, several proposal for Horizon Europe calls are currently being prepared

- HORIZON-INFRA-2023-EOSC-01-01: Science Cluster Consolidation and Open Calls -> OSCARS proposal
- HORIZON-INFRA-2023-SURV-01-01: Services related to Climate Change Risks
- HORIZON-INFRA-2023-DEV-01-04: EGI + ENV RIs -> ENVRI-Hub
- HORIZON-INFRA-2023-EOSC-01-03 – OpenAire + science clusters

4.24 23rd EB meeting, 28 March 2023, virtual

Meeting minutes

1. Welcome and approval of agenda Helen Glaves

As Karlina could not stay until the end of the meeting it was suggested to start with the topic ENVRI Community at the EGU23. This Agenda ([file](#), slide 2) was approved.

2. ENVRI Community at the EGU23 Karlina Ozolina

Karlina gave an overview on the plan for the ENVRI booth at the EGU 2023 ([file](#), slide 3 – 10). Helen suggested to forward the list of ENVRI lunch talks to her and she will forward it to the comms people of EGU so they will appear in the EGU-today newsletters. Ulpu was also interested in this list to forward it to the BEERi. Andreas volunteered to give an overview on ENVRI-FAIR and the ENVRI-Hub as one of the lunch talks. But it turned out that the list of talks was already full. Jacco mentioned that the time for the talks was a bit extended, it should be 15min and 5min for discussion. Helen mentioned that the EPOS booth will be next or close to the ENVRI booth. They have also planned lunch talks.

3. Status of the project - project monitoring, deliverables, milestones, final periodic report) Katrin Seemeyer

Katrin gave an overview on the status of the project ([file](#), slide 11 – 20).

The project officer from the REA has changed. The new project officer is Enrico Pellizari. As already announced at the ENVRI week 2023, the final project review meeting has been cancelled. However, there will be a project monitoring, i.e. the deliverables, milestones and the technical report of the third reporting period will be assessed by the one reviewer which has been assigned – Natalia Beloff. The steps for the project monitoring were shown ([file](#), slide 13), but for the ENVRI-FAIR consortium nothing changes. We will submit the deliverables and milestones as scheduled and submit the final technical report on 25 September 2023.

Concerning the timeline for the preparation of the technical report, the due date for the beneficiary reports was shifted to 30 June 2023 to give the beneficiaries a bit more time to prepare them. All the other due dates stay the same.

It was pointed out that the recommendations and comments from the project review should be considered and addressed in the work package reports. A summary of the recommendations and comments is available [here](#)

<https://fileshare.icos-cp.eu/apps/onlyoffice/s/B8e2HegfP4ZXaws?fileId=2821569>

and the whole report from the project review is available [here](#) <https://iagos-comm.iek.fz-juelich.de/dmsf/files/6851/view> (see also [file](#), slide 15).

On slides 17 – 20 ([file](#)) deliverables and milestones are listed which are not yet submitted or reached.

4. ENVRI-FAIR final event

Andreas reported on the current status for an ENVRI-FAIR final event ([file](#), slide 21).

Although, not all members of the EB might be necessary the EB members were asked to reserve the 20 and 21 June 2023 in their calendar.

5. ESFRI Landscape Analysis Andreas Petzold

Andreas presented the concept for the new ESFRI Landscape Analysis for the Environmental domain ([file](#), slide 22 - 27) and asked for input from the subdomains (Atmosphere – Andreas, Cathrine, Marine – Thierry, Solid Earth – Helen, Keith, Biodiversity / Ecosystems – Dario, Alberto).

6. ENVRI-Hub - ENVRI-Hub NEXT proposal

Andreas presented a summary of the proposal for the further development of the ENVRI-Hub ([file](#), slide 28 – 30) – the ENVRI-Hub NEXT proposal.

In the discussion it was asked if the text of the proposal would be made available. Andreas will check within the consortium if they all agree. There are also 2 additional proposals to the same call (HORIZON-INFRA-2023-DEV-01-04) from the ENVRI cluster. One from the marine domain the proposal is called AMRIT and one from the Biodiversity / Ecosystems domain, the ENVRI-TERRA proposal. Thierry for AMRIT and Dario for ENVRI-TERRA ([file](#), slide 44 – 46) will check if the text of the proposals can be made available to the ENVRI-FAIR community.

7. Other proposals

Other proposal recently submitted were briefly introduced

OS Trails (HORIZON-INFRA-2023-EOSC-01-03) – Keith Jeffery ([file](#), slide 32 – 36)

OSCARS – Andreas Petzold ([file](#), slide 37 – 40)

IRISCC – Valerie Thouret, presented by Andreas Petzold ([file](#), slide 41)

ENVRINNOV – Paolo Laj, presented by Andreas Petzold ([file](#), slide 42 – 43)

ENVRI-TERRA – Dario Papale ([file](#), slide 44 – 46)

8. Report on RDA Jacco Konijn

Jacco gave a brief report on the ENVRI-FAIR collocated event at the RDA Plenary meeting in Gothenburg last week. The meeting was very successful. There was a good audience not only in the room but also virtually. In the panel discussion there not only panellists from ENVRI-FAIR but also from EOSC Future, EGI and GOFAIR Foundation.

Keith Jeffery reported that at the Plenary part ENVRI-FAIR was presented at the meeting of the ESIP/RDA Earth, Space, and Environmental Sciences IG, which was received very well.

9. AOB Helen Graves

none

10. Decisions

none

11. Action items

Agenda Item	Action	Responsibility	Due date
2.	Sent list of lunch talks to Helen	Karlina, Laurent	asap
5.	Contact leaders of the subdomains for input to the ESFRI Landscape Analysis	Andreas	This week
6.	Contact consortium if proposals for ENVRI-Hub NEXT, AMRIT and ENVRI-TERRA can be made available	Andreas, Thierry, Dario	

12.

4.25 24th EB meeting, 31 May 2023, virtual

Meeting minutes

1. Welcome and approval of agenda

Helen Graves

As Angeliki could not stay until the end of the meeting it was suggested to start with the topics ENVRI-FAIR Lund event and HORIZON-INFRA-2024-EOSC-01-01 call. This change in the agenda ([file](#), slide 2) was approved.

2. ENVRI-FAIR Lund event Andreas Petzold

Andreas gave an overview on date and location of the Lund event and the agenda ([file](#), slide 11 – 13). **Participants from ENVRI-FAIR are very welcome to join the event in person**, but participation in Lund is not mandatory. The event will also be streamed. As soon as the connection details are available, they will be distributed. All participants from ENVRI-FAIR are invited to also join the dinner on 20 June 2023 at 18:00 CEST. If you want to join the dinner, please add your name to the poll here <https://www.terminplaner.dfn.de/z6WyWpuhDJWEHxaW> **2 June 2023**. Participants until from Lund can also spread the word about this event in Lund and invite people to join.

In the discussion it was asked if people from the high-level event are allowed to go to other buildings, as the building is about 10min walk from the main building where the high-level event takes place. The high-level event is by invitation only.

It was suggested that Alex Vermeulen who will be on the panel in one of the discussions of the high-level event will announce the ENVRI-FAIR event there.

Concerning the invitations, it was asked if somebody has access to the list of participants in the high-level event which Emmanuel has. Andreas will send out invitations this week.

The people from Lund are free to spread the word and invite people from the University to attend in person.

A newsletter will be sent out to the ENVRI community next week.

Other clusters will also be invited to participate remotely.

3. HORIZON-INFRA-2024-EOSC-01-01 call Andreas Petzold

Andreas presented the HORIZON-INFRA-2023-EOSC-01-01 call ([file](#), slide 14 – 17) which could be a continuation for ENVRI and a way to keep the ENVRI community together. Peter Thijsse (Marine subdomain) and Cathrine Lund Myhre (Atmosphere subdomain) agreed that it is a relevant call for the ENVRI community. Mature RIs from the ENVRI community or even wider which can provide data and services are targeted. Interested RIs from ENVRI-FAIR should approach Copernicus / Climate Adapt / (GEOSS) for collaboration. Andreas (the coordinating team) will contact the subdomain teams by email next week to introduce the process and ask who is interested in this call. In Lund we will discuss how to proceed in Lund.

4. Status of the project - final periodic report, deliverables, milestones) Katrin Seemeyer

Katrin gave an overview on the status of the project ([file](#), slide 3 - 10).

For the final periodic report, the preparation of the beneficiary report will be organised within the work packages. The important next deadline is the submission of the WP reports to the project office on **21 July 2023**.

The status of most of the deliverables was reported before the meeting. In the meeting it was stated that D4.4 there is still some work to do, also in D11.4 and D2.4. The status of milestones MS13 and MS14 is not clear yet, Keith will explore. Anca will explore the status of MS11.

All deliverables and milestone reports must be submitted in the final and reviewed version to the project office until **26 June 2023**.

5. AOB Anca Hienola

none

6. Decisions

none

7. Action items

Agenda Item	Action	Responsibility	Due date
2.	Send out invitation to Lund event	Andreas	This week
2.	Add you name to the poll if you would like to join the dinner https://www.terminplaner.dfn.de/z6WyWpuhDJWEHxaW	All	2 June 2023
2.	Spread the word of the event among people from Lund	People from Lund University	
2.	Contact Alex to announce the event	Andreas	
3.	Contact EB / contacts RIs with information on HORIZON-INFRA-2024-EOSC-01-01 call	Andreas	This week
4.	Status of MS13 and MS14	Keith	Asap
4.	Status of MS11	Anca	asap

5 Board of European Environmental Research Infrastructures

The Board of European Environmental Research Infrastructures (BEERi) is an advisory panel consisting of senior representatives (RI directors or coordinators) of the environmental domain RIs, providing direct advice to the ENVRI-FAIR project management and giving a strategic view to the project progress, acting as internal advisory board representing the needs of environmental RIs. It is

organised by WP3 and chaired by different members of BEERi. The BEERi had at least two meetings per year.

BEERi was chaired within ENVRI-FAIR initially by Sanna Sorvari Sundet (from January 2019 to November 2019), then by Ingrid Puillat (from to November 2019 to June 2022) and finally by Werner Kutsch (from June 2022 onwards). During the lifetime of ENVRI-FAIR, BEERi has met both in person and virtually, the physical BEERi meetings Physical meeting were usually organised in junction with the ENVRI weeks.

More details can be found in D3.2 - BEERi activity report

6 Annex I – ENVRI week 2019 – ENVRI-FAIR Kick-Off meeting

More information on the ENVRI-FAIR Kick-Off meeting can be found in deliverable [D1.1 - Organization of project Kick-off meeting, including a Steering Committee and a General Assembly meeting](#).

7 Annex II – ENVRI week 2020 – Dresden, Germany Agenda

AGENDA FOR THE ENVRI WEEK IN HOTEL ELBFLORENZ DRESDEN (GERMANY), 3-7 Feb 2020

Please note that additional parallel sessions are not desired in slots marked with a horizontal line.

	Start	End	Breaks	Room Galilei (Plenary room)	Room Michelangelo	Room Medici	Room Maclavelli	Room Da Vinci
Monday	11:00	12:00				Registration (Foyer)		
	12:00	13:00	Lunch at hotel restaurant					
	13:00	13:30		Welcome by Project Coordinator				
	13:30	15:30		ENVRI-FAIR and the ENVRI community in the ESRI, ECDC and FAIR landscapes - Plenary -				
	15:30	16:00	Coffee break					
Tuesday	16:00	17:00		Communications strategy and tools				
	17:00	18:00		Motivation and expectations of the consortium with respect to the project (Discussion)				
	18:00	20:00			Reception (Foyer; possibility to set up stands with roll-ups, posters, etc.)			
	09:00	10:30		Atmosphere subdomain meeting (WP8 working meeting)	Marine subdomain meeting (WP9 working meeting)	Solid Earth subdomain meeting (WP10 working meeting)	Ecosystem/ Biodiversity subdomain meeting (WP11 working meeting)	
	10:30	11:00	Coffee break					
Wednesday	11:00	12:30		Atmosphere subdomain meeting (WP8 working meeting)	Marine subdomain meeting (WP9 working meeting)	Solid Earth subdomain meeting (WP10 working meeting)	Ecosystem/ Biodiversity subdomain meeting (WP11 working meeting)	
	12:30	13:30	Lunch at hotel restaurant					
	13:30	14:30		Atmosphere subdomain meeting (WP8 working meeting)	Marine subdomain meeting (WP9 working meeting)	Solid Earth subdomain meeting (WP10 working meeting)	Ecosystem/ Biodiversity subdomain meeting (WP11 working meeting)	
	14:30	15:30		Progress update by the subdomains - Plenary- (WP8-11)				
	15:30	16:00	Coffee break					
Thursday	16:00	17:00		WPS Task Force 1 working session: ENVRI Catalogue of Services (FAIR)	WPS Task Force 3 working session: PIDs identification types and registries (FAIR)		WPS Task Force 4 working session: Triple stores and data storage certification (FAIR)	
	17:00	18:00		WPS Task Force 6 working session: User oriented cross-domain demonstration cases in e.g. Jupyter (IR)	WPS Task Force 5 working session: Licenses citation and usage tracking (of data and VRI) (IR)		WPS Task Force 2 working session: ENVRI (VO) AAJ implementation (A)	
	18:00	20:00				Policy working group meeting (by invitation only)		
	16:00	20:15		Guided tour through the old town				
	09:00	10:00		Summary of the outcomes of the WPS Task Force working sessions				
Friday	10:00	10:30	Coffee break					
	10:30	11:45		General assembly (incl. Remarks from the financial administration)				
	11:45	12:30		Policy landscape in the ENVRI domain - Discussion -				
	12:30	13:30	Lunch at hotel restaurant					
	13:30	14:30		FAIRness training and capacity building - Progress and challenges	Innovation activities and alignment with national and international stakeholders (WP3 working meeting)	Policy working group meeting (by invitation only)	WPS working meeting	
Saturday	14:30	15:30		First training event for data center staff: Terminologies for ENVRI: Why, What & How (Part I)	Links to other ESRI clusters		Redmine training	
	15:30	16:00	Coffee break					
	16:00	18:00		First training event for data center staff: Terminologies for ENVRI: Why, What & How (Part II)	Executive Board meeting			
	18:30	22:30		Social Dinner (Kuppelrestaurant in der Yenfelder)				
	09:00	10:30		Open ENVRI community meeting (Part I): What ENVRI community and ENVRI-FAIR do, what do they offer to you and how you can get involved	WP7 working meeting (Development of ontologies, IRM etc. in the knowledge Base)			Marine subdomain meeting (WP9 working meeting)
Sunday	10:30	11:00	Coffee break					
	11:00	12:30		Open ENVRI community meeting (Part II): What is the role of ENVRI community in the development of ECDC and how we can collaborate with the ECDC development groups and projects	WP7 working meeting (WP7 discussion)			Marine subdomain meeting (WP9 working meeting)
	12:30	13:30	Lunch at hotel restaurant		Redmine training			
	13:30	14:30				BEER meeting (by invitation only)		
	14:30	15:30						
Monday	15:30	16:00	Coffee break					
	16:00	18:00				BEER meeting (by invitation only)		
	09:00	10:30				BEER meeting (by invitation only)		
	10:30	11:00	Coffee break					
	11:30	12:30				BEER meeting (by invitation only)		
12:30	13:30	Lunch at hotel restaurant						

8 Annex III – ENVRI week 2021 – virtual meeting - Agenda

2021-02-01 Monday		speaker(s)		time
	Welcome, logistics and overview	Katrin Seemeyer, Andreas Petzold	45 min	13:00-13:45
	Summary of EOSC activities	Anca Hienola, Ari Asmi, Andreas Petzold	45 min	13:45-14:30
	-- coffee break (introduction WONDER) --		30 min	14:30-15:00
	WPS - FAIRness activities	Barbara Magagna, Alex Vermeulen, Angeliki Adamaki	45 min	15:00-15:45
	Report on training activities	Maggie Hellström, Jacco Konijn, Nicola Fiore	45 min	15:45-16:30
	-- Online reception (WONDER) --		45 min	16:30-17:15
2021-02-02 Tuesday				
	Task Forces - results and way forward	TF (co-)leads	90 min	09:00-10:30
	-- coffee break --		30 min	10:30-11:00
	Task Forces - results and way forward continued	TF (co-)leads	90 min	11:00-12:30
	-- lunch break --		60 min	12:30-13:30
	Subdomains - results and way forward	WP (co-)leads	90 min	13:30-15:00
	-- coffee break --		30 min	15:00-15:30
	Subdomains - results and way forward continued	WP (co-)leads	60 min	15:30-16:30
2021-02-03 Wednesday				
	ENVRI Knowledge base	Zhiming Zhao, Daniele Bailo, Dick Schaap	45 min	09:00-9:45
	Technical workshop on common development support (separate registration required)	Zhiming Zhao, Daniele Bailo, Dick Schaap	75 min	09:45-11:00
	-- coffee break --		30 min	11:00-11:30
	ENVRI Communications	Magdalena Brus	45 min	11:30-12:15
	-- lunch break --		60 min	12:15-13:15
	Policy Landscape Analysis	Helen Glaves, Ari Asmi	45 min	13:15-14:15
	EB meeting (EB members)		60 min	14:15-15:15
	-- coffee break --		30 min	15:15-15:45
	General Assembly (GA members)		60 min	15:45-16:45
2021-02-04 Thursday				
	Training event (separate registration required)	Maggie Hellström, Jacco Konijn, Nicola Fiore	120 min	09:00-11:00
	-- coffee break --		30 min	11:00-11:30
	Training event continued	Maggie Hellström, Jacco Konijn, Nicola Fiore	120 min	11:30-13:30
	-- lunch break --		60 min	13:30-14:30
	Official Closing of the meeting by Project Coordinator	Andreas Petzold	30 min	14:30-15:00
	BEERi (for BEERi members)	Ingrid Puillat, Ulpu Leijala	120 min	15:00-17:00
2021-02-05 Friday				
	BEERi (for BEERi members) continued	Ingrid Puillat, Ulpu Leijala	180 min	09:00-12:00

9 Annex IV – ENVRI week 2022 – virtual meeting - Agenda

▼ Agenda

Chair	2022-01-31 Monday	speaker(s)	duration	time (CET)
	Welcome, logistics and overview	Katrin Seemeyer, Andreas Petzold	15 min	13:00-13:15
	Subdomain meetings	Subdomain (co-)leads	165 min	13:15-16:00
	2021-02-01 Tuesday			
Andreas Petzold / Ines Thelen	FAIRness, standards, harmonisation, requirements	Alex Vermeulen, Angeliki Adamaki	90 min	10:00-11:30
Helen Glaves / Ines Thelen	EOSC activities, science clusters, EOSC Future	Anca Hienola, Ari Asmi, Andreas Petzold, Keith Jeffery	60 min	11:30-12:30
	-- lunch break --			
Andreas Petzold / Ines Thelen	Reports from the subdomain meetings	subdomain (co-)leads	60 min	13:30-14:30
	-- coffee break --			
	General Assembly (GA members)		60 min	14:45-15:45
	2021-02-02 Wednesday			
Andreas Petzold / Ines Thelen	Test run project review - first part		120 min	10:00-12:00
	-- lunch break --			
	Test run project review - second part		60 min	13:00-14:00
	-- coffee break --			
	EB meeting (EB members + invited guests)		120 min	14:15-16:15
	2021-02-03 Thursday			
Anca Hienola / Ines Thelen	ENVRI-Hub (demonstration, sustainability)	Rita Gomes, Andreas Petzold, Ari Asmi	120 min	10:00-12:00
	-- lunch break --			
Anca Hienola / Ines Thelen	ENVRI Communications	Katri Ahlgren, Karlina Ozolina	45 min	13:00-13:45
	Official Closing of the meeting by Project Coordinator	Andreas Petzold	15 min	13:45-14:00
	-- coffee break --			
	ENVRI community meeting	Katri Ahlgren, Rita Gomes, Gergely Sipos and others	75 min	14:15-15:30
	-- coffee break --			
	Social gathering in Wonder		open end	15:45-late
	2021-02-04 Friday			
	BEERi (for BEERi members)	Werner Kutsch, Ulpu Leijala	120 min	09:00-11:00
	-- coffee break --			
	BEERi (for BEERi members) continued	Werner Kutsch, Ulpu Leijala	90 min	11:30-13:00

10 Annex V – ENVRI week 2023 – Leipzig, Germany - Agenda

	Plenary	room Atmosphere	room Marine	room Solid Earth	room Biodiv./Ecosyst.	Time
M o n d a y	registration					09:00-12:30
	Lunch (hotel restaurant)					12:30-13:30
	Welcome, logistics and overview					13:30-14:00
	WP5 Workshop					14:00-15:30
	Coffee (Foyer)					15:30-16:00
	Communications Session					16:00-17:00
T u e s d a y	reception					18:00-20:00
	WP5 Task Forces Final Event					09:00-10:30
	Coffee (Foyer)					10:30-11:00
	WP5 Task Forces Final Event					11:00-12:30
	Lunch (hotel restaurant)					12:30-13:30
	Atmosphere		Marine	Solid Earth	Biodiv./Ecosyst.	13:30-15:00
	Coffee (Foyer)					15:00-15:30
Atmosphere		Marine	Solid Earth	Biodiv./Ecosyst.	15:30-16:30	
EB Meeting					16:30-18:00	
W e d n e s d a y	Reports from the subdomain meetings					09:00-10:30
	Coffee (Foyer)					10:30-11:00
	Interactive training session - Identify and address end users expectations		WP7 working session	WP3 session		11:00-12:30
	Lunch (hotel restaurant)					12:30-13:30
	Policy Workshop		Panel discussion on PID issues			13:30-15:30
	Coffee (Foyer)					15:30-16:00
General Assembly					16:00-18:00	
T h u r s d a y	Social Dinner at the Felix Club					19:00-open end
	ENVRI - EOSC Future					09:00-10:00
	Coffee (Foyer)					10:00-10:30
	FAIRness					10:30-12:30
	Lunch (hotel restaurant)					12:30-13:30
	Official Closing					13:30-14:00
	Open ENVRI community meeting					14:00-15:30
Coffee (Foyer)					15:30-16:00	
BEERi Meeting					16:00-18:00	
F r i d a y	BEERi Meeting				09:00-10:30	
	Coffee (Foyer)					10:30-11:00
	BEERi Meeting				11:00-12:30	
	Lunch (hotel restaurant)					12:30-13:30

11 Annex II Glossary

BEERi	Board of European Environmental Research Infrastructures
EB	executive board
CA	consortium agreement
GA	general assembly
WP	work package